

ANALYTICAL REVIEW OF RESEARCHES ON YAM FOR INCREASED AND SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION

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Abstract: *There are about 600 species of Dioscoreaceae but a few are cultivated for food or medicine out of which only six are economically important staple species. Yams originated from tropical forests or savannas where there are sharply demarcated rainy and dry seasons. Yam remains the most preferred starchy staple for many people in yam belt of West Africa. The major edible species of African origin are white Guinea yam (*D. rotundata* Poir.), yellow Guinea yam (*D. cayenensis* Lam.), and trifoliate or bitter yam (*D. dumetorum* Kunth). Edible species from Asia include water or greater yam (*D. alata* L.); and lesser yam (*D. esculenta* [Lour.] Burkill). Nigeria is the largest producer of yams contributing 65.5% to global production. Yams provide essential nutrients for millions of people, contributing to food security but also deeply intertwined with socio-cultural practices, serving as special gifts, ritual objects, and centerpiece of vibrant New Yam Festivals in various regions of the world. Yam production has been on the decline in the world because it is constrained by limited availability of planting materials, high cost of farm operation, depletion of soil fertility, degradation of soil physical properties and inadequate use of fertilizers as well as poor funding for research. This review covers relevance and prevalence of cultivation, production areas, environment for good yam production, soils for good yam production, soil nutrient management techniques, fertilization and fertilizer requirements, fertilizer recommendations for individual yam species, plant population and sett weight, intercropping/mixed cropping, weed, pests and diseases and yam yield, processing/composition and storage, yam improvement, comparative economic analysis, and major constraints on yam production for purposes of providing relevant information for increased and sustainable production.*

INTRODUCTION

There are about 600 species of Dioscoreaceae but a few are cultivated for food or medicine out of which only six are economically important staple species. Yams originated from tropical forests or savannas where there are sharply demarcated rainy and dry seasons. Yam remains the most preferred starchy staple for many people in yam belt of West Africa. The major edible species of African origin are white Guinea yam (*D. rotundata* Poir.), yellow Guinea yam (*D. cayenensis* Lam.), and trifoliate or bitter yam (*D. dumetorum* Kunth). Edible species from Asia include water or greater yam (*D. alata* L.); and lesser yam (*D. esculenta* [Lour.] Burkill). Nigeria is the largest producer of yams contributing 65.5% to global production. Yams provide essential nutrients for millions of people, contributing to food security but also deeply intertwined with socio-cultural practices, serving as special gifts, ritual objects, and centerpiece of vibrant New Yam Festivals in various regions of the world. Yam production has been on the decline in the world because it is constrained by limited availability of planting materials, high cost of farm operation, depletion of soil fertility, degradation of soil physical properties and inadequate use of fertilizers as well as poor funding for research. This review covers relevance and prevalence of cultivation, production areas, environment for good yam production, soils for good yam production, soil nutrient management

techniques, fertilization and fertilizer requirements, fertilizer recommendations for individual yam species, plant population and sett weight, intercropping/mixed cropping, weed, pests and diseases and yam yield, processing/composition and storage, yam improvement, comparative economic analysis, and major constraints on yam production for purposes of providing relevant information for increased and sustainable production.

1. Relevance and Prevalence of Cultivation

“Yams” in their exact sense according to Coursey and Martin (1970) refer to the useful members of the genus *Dioscorea*. They constitute the largest genus of the Dioscoreaceae with over 600 species but only a few are cultivated for food or medicine out of which six are economically important staple species (Purseglove, 1972). Furthermore the yams which are important as crop plants originated in tropical forests or savannas where there are sharply demarcated rainy and dry seasons. During the rainy season the plants grow as vines which twine often for many metres, through trees or undergrowth but in cultivation the vines are usually trained on stakes, strings or wires. At the end of the season, the vines die down and the plant persists through the dry season in the form of dormant tubers.

Yam is a domesticated species of the Dioscoreaceae produced primarily in Nigeria.

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Yam (*Dioscorea* species) is an economically important tuber crop in tropical and subtropical regions of the world. It is an important crop in West Africa, both as a food and for cultural purposes and widely grown in a range of soils under improved and subsistence cultivation techniques (Diby et al., 2011). Yam production is constrained by limited availability of planting materials, high cost of farm operation, depletion of soil fertility and degradation of soil physical properties and inadequate use of fertilizers (Diby et al., 2011).

Yam remains the most preferred starchy staple for many people in yam belt of West Africa (Kenyon, 2006). However, productivity of yam in the main yam growing belt of West Africa is continually on the decline and cannot meet the present demand. FAO-SAT (2004) stated that, in Nigeria, the average yield of yam appears to have been steadily declining over the last 8-10 years. Yam production is constrained by limited availability of planting material, high cost of farm operation, depletion of soil fertility and degradation of soil physical properties and inadequate use of fertilizers. In spite of increased demand for yam, its production and productivity had been declining. Tuber yield decline from 11t/ha in 1995 to 3.5 t/ha in 2007 was associated with the decline in soil fertility (Agbaje et al., 2005).

Yellow yam (*Dioscorea cayenensis*) and white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) are second to cassava as the most important and cultivated tropical tuber and root crops. They are widely

cultivated in Nigeria, and because of their multi-purpose uses, they occupy a principal place in the farming systems of the humid tropical region. While Africa alone represents 90% of the world production of yams, Nigeria accounts for over 70% of the world production (Okoh, 2004). White yam is one of the major food crops produced in Nigeria mainly by traditional farmers.

The major edible species of African origin are white Guinea yam (*D. rotundata* Poir.), yellow Guinea yam (*D. cayenensis* Lam.), and trifoliolate or bitter yam (*D. dumetorum* Kunth). Edible species from Asia include water or greater yam (*D. alata* L.), and lesser yam (*D. esculenta* [Lour.] Burkill). Cush-cush yam (*D. trifida* L.) originated from the Americas. White Guinea yam and water yam are the most important food yams in terms of cultivation and utilization. These tubers which are the natural food storage organs are the economically useful part of the plant (Coursey and Martin, 1970). Yam tubers may be eaten with sauce direct after boiling, roasting, or frying in oil. Though the use of yam as food dates back to the earliest days of man's history, true yam-based agriculture appeared to have developed independently in West Africa and Southeast Asia around 3,000 years B.C. (Coursey, 1967). This was attributed to the cultural interaction between pre-agricultural peoples who exploited wild yams for food with early Neolithic grain-producing agriculturalists. The yam species did not originate from the same source. According to Coursey (1967) and

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FAO (1990) *Dioscorea alata* (water yam) and *D. esculenta* (Chinese yams) originated from Southeast Asia, *D. cayenensis* (yellow yam) and *D. rotundata* (white yam) from West Africa. *D. dumetorum* (cluster yams), *D. bulbifera* (aerial yam) and *D. prachensilis* were also grown in West Africa. The common species in Southern China and Japan are *D. opposita* and *D.*

japonica while *D. trifida* is thought to have originated from America. Table 1 shows the varieties popularly grown in Africa, Asia and America (Coursey, 1971). The cultivation of yams not only antedates European contacts, but also the beginning of the use of iron tools in Africa around 2000 years ago (Coursey and Booth, 1977).

Table 1: The varieties popularly grown in Africa, Asia and America

Continent	Yam varieties				
Africa	<i>D. rotundata</i> (white yam)	<i>D. alata</i> (water yam)	<i>D. cayenensis</i> (yellow yam)	<i>D. dumetorum</i> (cluster yam)	<i>D. bulbifera</i> (aerial yam)
Asia	<i>D. prachensilis</i>	<i>D. esculenta</i> (Chinese yams)	<i>D. opposita</i>	<i>D. japonica</i>	
America	<i>D. trifida</i>				

Source: (Coursey, 1971).

In West Africa yam cultivation according to Coursey (1971) was originally a purely indigenous development and the main species grown, the typical West African white yam (*D. rotundata*) is not known elsewhere in the world except as a comparatively recent introduction.

The great amount of rituals, ceremonies and superstition surround almost every aspect of yam cultivation and utilization and history also indicates the great antiquity of their use in West Africa. Hence, it is perhaps no coincidence that the great states of the second millennium A.D. in the forest zone of West Africa namely Ashanti in Ghana, Ife and Benin in Nigeria arose where yam was the staple food (Coursey, 1967). It has

been noted that of all the tropical food crops virtually none is as closely associated with particular cultural area as the certain species of yam with West Africa (Coursey and Booth, 1977).

In all societies where yams are major crops as in West Africa, Malaysia and the Caribbean, Coursey (1984) observed that they were crops of prestige and had acquired heavy burden of religion and magical significance that hardly applied to any other tropical crops. Grebremeskel and Oyewole (1987) also recognized yam as a prestigious food and demand for it often increased with income such that the income elasticity was positive but often less than unity. Yams according to them were

often produced almost exclusively for human consumption, for instance, in sub-Saharan African yam accounted for 21% of all roots and tubers consumed and for up to 55% of such crops in West African sub-region.

However, on some Islands of Pohnpei, East Caroline Islands, additional value was placed on yam. According to Raynor et al., (1992) yam is the most important crop on the Pohnpei Island in the Eastern Carolines and features prominently in the traditional prestige system and yams of large size are produced which are highly suitable for prestige purposes.

Visser (1975) also observed that the Ando people of Ivory Coast cultivated numerous edible yams for some various medicinal, culinary, ritual and household uses. The people of Western Abalam of Papua New Guinea displayed annual cycle of social conflicts and births which was a function of a system of ritual beliefs involved in the growing of ceremonial yams (Scaghion and Condon, 1979). This sociorhythmic ritual complex involved adherence to various taboos. Yam is not only of nutritional importance, but also a sacred value, object of grandiose cultural festivals that only uncontrollable events such as the COVID-19 pandemic can shake (Pamphile and Nassirou, 2020).

Several pharmacologically active ingredients such as one used in the manufacture of sex hormone and cortisone have also been found in yams (Okigbo, 1986). Wild yams with high saponin content are often used as precursors

for the synthesis of some hormones and as a "natural alternative" to estrogen therapy for symptoms of menopause, infertility, menstrual problems, and many other conditions, but there is no good scientific evidence to support any of these uses (WebMD, 2025). Various biochemical approaches used to identify yams such as chromatography and electrophoretic separation of soluble proteins or selected enzyme on polyacrylamide or starch gels (Ikediobi and Igboanusi, 1983) may help get varieties appropriate for different uses.

The major nutrient obtained from yam food is carbohydrate but Bell (1983) stated that yam may supply a substantial portion of the manganese and phosphorus requirements of adults, and to lesser degree, the copper, iron and magnesium requirements. Elkims (1979) earlier observed that for all minerals except calcium, yams on the average are richer than cassava, cocoyams and sweet potatoes. Baquar and Oke (1976) have shown that some clones of *D. rotundata* and *D. dumentorum* have protein contents between 3-2 to 13.9% dry weight, hence some yams are superior to maize and rice in useable proteins. Obidiegwu et al., (2020) stated that a yam meal could supply 100% of the energy and protein, 130% of calcium and 80% of iron needs of an adult. Eka (1985) reports that most yams are also rich in phosphorus and some vitamins like thiamine, riboflavin, niacin and ascorbic acid. Egbe and Treche (1984) analysed ninety-eight cultivars from eight species of yams and found high contents of Mg,

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P, Ca, K and Na. Egbe and Treche (1984), however, noted that there are variabilities in chemical composition of yam tuber and this composition may vary even within the same cultivar depending on the environmental conditions under which the tuber was produced. In general, however, the importance of yams is associated more with its food value presently.

A study by FAO (1985) showed that yams give more yield and more calories than cereals and millets. Martin (1979) pointed out that the assumption that yam can only be used as resource for calories was false because the protein contents of some yam varieties approach those of cereals and opined that since yams could be used in a variety of forms, and are of high maturational value, they merit intensity of study that they have never yet received so that they could be produced more efficiently. Chandra (1979) showed that it was necessary to step up the production of yams and other root crops in Fiji Islands in the urban hinterland of Fiji to avoid possible malnutrition of the low income population. However, apparent neglect of researches into yams in the past has been attributed partly to histo-cultural problems arising from non-mention of yams in the Bible as opposed to grains (Coursey, 1976).

Certain factors often lead to adoption of certain varieties in preference or in combination with existing varieties in some areas. In Puerto Rico, for instance, a new variety of *D. rotundata* (Guinea Negro) introduced from Jamaica was evaluated and compared with the local cultivar

Habanero. The study showed that the introduced cultivar not only yielded highly but had a shorter dormant period than Habanero and can thus be planted out of season with high yields. Thus, by planting both cultivars at different times there was always yam in the market all year round (Ramirez et al., 1984). Again Lebot (2009) observed that the people of Western Samoa preferred *D. nemmularia* to *D. alata* and *D. esculenta* because of the more solid texture and higher dry matter of *D. nemmularia*. Based on the population of certain varieties in some countries their performance was evaluated by Coursey and Martin (1970). Table 2 shows the yields of *D. alata*, *D. Esculenta*, *D. rotundata* and *D. cayenensis* in various countries that grow them. Though from the *D. rotundata* grown in Nigeria gave the lowest value of 16.2 t/ha, Nigeria is the largest yam producing country in Africa and has been leading the entire world for a long time. Most of the world production of yam is from Africa (about 96%) with Nigeria alone accounting for nearly 75% of the total world production (Opara, 2023).

Nigeria has a total production of 18.3 million Mg from 1.5 million ha (FAO, 2004). Despite the importance of yam, its production in Nigeria has not been accorded the needed attention (Orkwor and Asadu, 1999). This was reflected in the fall in output percentage growth rate of yam from 42% in 1990 to 16.3% in 2001 despite the increase in land devoted for the production of the crop from 1270 million hectares to 2742

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million hectares in the same period (Federal Ministry of Agriculture, FMA 2001). Yam farmers and researchers need a variety of encouragement from government and donor agencies to increase their research on yam and production activities in Nigeria.

Yams, cultivated from approximately 600 *Dioscorea* species, hold immense significance in Nigeria, contributing 65.5% to global production. Beyond providing essential nutrients for millions of people and contributing to food security, yam is still deeply intertwined with socio-cultural practices, serving as special gifts, ritual objects, and centerpiece of vibrant New Yam Festivals in various regions, thus elevating its status the more (Olatunde, 2024). Yam (*Dioscorea* spp) is important for food security in West Africa which produces more than 90% of the worldwide production (FAO, 2009). Besides their importance as food source, yam also plays a significant role in the socio-cultural lives of people in some producing regions like the celebrated New Yam Festival in West Africa (Osunde and Orhevba, 2009) and wedding ceremonies in Oceania (O'Sullivan, 2007).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) (personal Communication, 2025) summary on the importance of yam is that “yam is a crucial food and cash crop in West Africa, playing a significant role in food security and livelihoods. It's a major source of calories and protein, and holds high cultural significance, often

associated with social rites and ceremonies. Cultivation is concentrated in the humid and southern Guinea savannah agroecologies, with Nigeria being the largest global producer”.

Root and tuber crops (RTB) have been playing increasingly important roles in food security and in meeting global dietary requirements (Adeniji et al., 2012). Among the RTB's, yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) holds unparalleled significance as both a staple food and a cash crop in Africa's sub-humid tropics, West Africa accounted for 96% of the world yam production figure of 88.3 Mt and the current estimates put the Nigeria production figure at 61.2 MT representing 72% of West African production (Aleman et al., 1996).

Yam is primarily grown as subsistence crop, heavily reliant on natural environmental conditions but its demand far exceeds supply due to low productivity, which is constrained by several biotic and environmental factors (Olatunji et al., 2024). With the global population projected to reach 9.6 billion by 2050, enhancing the productivity of vital food crops like yam, while maintaining environmental sustainability, is vital for ensuring food security (Atiri et al., 2003).

In Nigeria, institutions like the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA) prioritize yam breeding endeavors aimed at developing novel varieties that meet end-users' preferences, encompassing both farmers and consumers. This focus revolves around critical traits such as consistent tuber quality, high

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yield, less oxidative tuber flesh browning tendency, increased dry matter content, and resistance against yam mosaic virus and anthracnose disease (Aleman et al., 1996, Azeteh et al., 2019, et al., (2021a).

Yam is a main staple for millions of people globally and especially in West Africa. Approximately, there are about 600 species of yam of which an estimated 10 species are consumed and cultivated worldwide. Interestingly, the “yam belt” zone of West Africa which comprises Nigeria, Cote d’Ivoire, Benin, Ghana and Togo account for 95% of this global yam production. Ranked as the fourth most important root and tuber crop behind potato, sweet potato and cassava truly confirms the role yam plays in food security and the socio-economic fortunes of the people. (Tostain et al., 2007; Jonathan et al., 2011; Toualy et al., 2014; Tamiru et al., 2017; Azeteh et al., 2019; FAOSTAT, 2021; Ita et al., 2020). Taxonomically, yam belongs to the family Dioscoreaceae of the order Dioscoreales (Liliflorae) and genus Dioscorea (Jonathan, 2019). According to FAO (2012), yam is the most valuable staple crop in Côte d’Ivoire, with over 7.2 million tonnes produced in 2018. It is reported that *D. rotundata* accounts for 75% of the yam trade in the country.

One of the *Dioscorea* species, *D. rotundata*, fondly known as “white yam or Guinea yam,” is native to West Africa. It is actually the most important food yam and accounts for 79% of the world’s total food yam production (IITA, 1995;

Jonathan et al., 2025). Interestingly, Nigeria produces 70% of this total (31.5 million tonnes annually) (Ezulike et al., 2006). To date, this record positions Nigeria as the largest producer of *D. rotundata* in the world. *D. rotundata* is the most famous and favoured yam variety among farmers and end consumers. Its advantageous potentials, which include exceptional agronomic traits, notable resistance to critical pests and diseases, adaptability to a variety of environmental conditions, and culinary attributes, make it eligible for agricultural improvement initiatives, commercial expansion, and international trade (Nwankwo, 2012; Singh, 2016; Omeonu et al., 2025). In general, research on new uses of yam will boost yam production and attract more entrepreneurs to yam farming business.

2. Production Areas

Yam production in the tropics is very important as yams serve as a very important source of good quality starch and some protein in the diets of most people. Yam is second to cereals as the most important food crop in West Africa (Course, 1967); Onwueme, 1978) and one of the corner-stones of Jamaican agricultural sector (Anonymous, 1972). In all societies where yams are major crops namely West Africa, Melanesia and the Caribbean, they are crops of prestige and have acquired heavy burden of religion and magical significance that hardly applies to any other tropical crop (Coursey, 1984). The cultivation of *D. rotundata* is indigenous to West Africa and is not known elsewhere except

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as a comparatively recent introduction (Coursey, 1976). Only twelve of the six hundred identified species of *Dioscorea* have been found to possess edible tubers. The most popular edible species in the tropics according to Ene and Okoli (1985) are *D. rotundata*/*D. cayenensis* complex, *D. alata*, *D. dumentorum*, *D. bulbifera* and *D. trifida*. The most important species of *Dioscorea* in the world and the most widely grown and eaten species in West Africa is *Dioscorea rotundata* Poir popularly known as white yam or white guinea yam (Okonkwo, 1985). Yams and cassava are the most widely grown and eaten tuber and root crops in southern Nigeria and are usually grown as intercrops by more than 80% of the farmers in the area (Unanma et al., 1985; Gebremeskel and Oyewole 1987). Upton (1967) also found that the main crops in most crop mixtures in southern Nigeria are yam and cassava with maize, okra, cowpeas and other vegetables as minor intercrops. According to Gebremeskel and Oyewole (1987) yam is a prestigious food and demand increases with income such that the income elasticity is positive but often less than unity, however, unlike cassava and sweet potato, yam is produced almost exclusively for human consumption and as a food source, yams are the second most important of root and tuber crops in countries that produce them. Okigbo (1986) also indicated that yams have some pharmaceutical uses, for instance, in the production of sex hormones and other similar drugs. In sub-Saharan Africa yam accounts for

21% of all roots and tubers consumed and for up to 55% of such crops in West African sub-region (Gebremeskel and Oyewole, 1987).

Yam production is a major component of farmers' agricultural or food crop activities in West Africa. West Africa accounts for 90-95% of the world's yam production (Aquah, 1991, FAO, 1998, out of which 71% is grown in Nigeria (Okwor, 1998).

In Nigeria according to Okorji (1986), about 80% of yams consumed were produced in the south eastern part of the country and most of the farmers were non-educated small-holder farmers whom Olayide (1980) had earlier indicated generally supply more than 90% of the food eaten by Nigerians. Nigeria according to FAO (1975) produced 74.3% of world yam and 76.8% of the Africa's production. Earlier, FAO (1974) has indicated that in 1974 Nigeria production was 81% (15 million tonnes) of all the yams produced in West Africa (18.4 million tonnes). According to Coursey (1984) the countries of the "yam zone" namely Nigeria, Benin, Togo, Ghana and Ivory Coast produced together more than 90% of the world total output of yam.

Yam is a multi-species crop consisting of approximately 600 species. Within the diverse array of yam species, White Guinea yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir) reigns supreme, flourishing extensively in West Africa's tropical regions, and supporting the livelihoods of over 400 million people, and its cultivation extends from Cameroon to Sierra Leone (Aleman et

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al.,1997; Asiedu et al., 2010 in Omeonu et al., 2025). Table 2 shows FAO, (2007) ranking of the 2006 production data of five major yam producing countries in “Yam-Belt Zone” of West Africa with production from Nigeria almost four

times the total from the other four countries. The production per ha is almost the same in Nigeria and Ghana (12.1 vs. 12 t/ha) followed by Benin (11.4 t/h and Togo (10.3 t/ha) all ahead of Côte d’Ivoire (8.9 t/h)

Figure 1: Map showing the key agro-ecologies of major yam producing countries in West Africa (Asiedu et al., 2010 in Omeonu et al., 2025).

Table 2: Five major yam producing countries in “Yam-Belt Zone of West Africa” and 2006 production data (FAO, 2007).

S/N	Country	Production Quantities (Tonnes)	Area Harvested (Hectares)
1	Nigeria	36 720 000	3 035 000
2	Côte d’Ivoire	4 800 000	540 000
3	Ghana	3 600 000	300 000
4	Benin	2 239 757	195 747
5	Togo	621 055	60 246

3. Environment for Good Yam Production

According to Buffard and Toure (1980) yam cultivation is very much dependent on climatic factors and it is often difficult to obtain tubers at a date very much different from normal harvest. Azih (1977) earlier observed that the distribution of yam cultivars and the methods of

farming adopted in various communities in Nigeria depended very much on the vegetation, pattern of rainfall, temperature, soil type and so on. This further explains the predominance of white yam (*D. rotundata*) in the drier savanna areas where soil is loose and yellow yam (*D. cayenensis*) in the rainforest areas where the soil is heavy and staking material readily

available. Dawson et al (1980) found that water controls the growth rates of yam to a far greater extent than other environmental factors and that low buck density, free-drainage and deep soils limited *Dioscorea* tuber growth rate by their inability to deliver without interruption, the required volumes of low tension water.

The pattern of yam growth has been reported (Sobulo, 1972; Njoku *et al.*, 1973). Onwueme (1975) reports three phases in yam growth and notes that in the second phase, which is after sprouting and emergence, there is a drastic increase in plant leaf area and this marks the transition of the plant from dependence on the sett to self-sufficiency. It is the stage of carbohydrate accumulation, hence tuber initiation occurs in this stage and this is usually in the tenth to eleventh week after planting. Enyi (1972) has also shown that there is a good linear relationship between leaf area duration and tuber yield but pointed out that tuber bulking rate increases with leaf area up to 490 dm² and decreases thereafter.

Leaf area index has been generally used as an index of photosynthetic capacity of the leaves (Doku, 1984), and as an important factor in yield determinations (Ferguson, 1973). Similarly, Samaravira *et al.* (1987) report that yams usually produce over two hundred leaves during their growth period and leaf number and duration are important parameters contribution to the yield potential of any crop.

Ferguson (1973) found that the amount of photosynthates available for translocation to

the developing tubers and the ability of the tubers to accept and translocate them were important factors in yield determinations. High light intensities have been found to increase the vegetative growth, flowering and bulbil formation of *D. bulbifera* (Buffard-Morel, 1981). The rate of translocation of assimilates from leaves of two white yams determined by a gravimetric method involving blocking of translocation by treating the leaf petiole with iodide alcohol showed that translocation increased with plant age and was higher during the day than at night and was affected by leaf position. Okezie (1987) subjected pre-sprouted minisett after six weeks of growth to short-day (10hr light-14 hr dark) and long-day (16hr light-8hr dark) conditions in a greenhouse and sampled weekly for tuberization. The result showed that despite the varied time of tuberization among plants, short-days induced more tuberization at the early growth phase than did long days. This observation was supported when less tuberization was obtained when light breaks were applied in the middle of the long dark period. The promotive effect of short-days on tuberization tended to diminish with the age of the plants prior to their exposure to the short-day treatments. Tuber initiation has been shown to be favoured by short-day length (Njoku, 1963) and Obigbesan (1977) also obtained high tuber yields of *D. rotundata* under short-day length. Again a photoperiod of greater than 12 hours was found to favour vine development and an increase in tuber yield of

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up to 30% was attributed to good vine development associated with long-day length (Purseglove, 1972). However, the photosynthetic capacity of yam was also found to be a function of the leaf area index (Doku, 1984). Annual rainfall requirements for good yam growth range from 1000 to 1600 mm well distributed over the growing seasons and most yam growing zones in southeastern Nigeria meet the rainfall requirement (Asadu, 1989). On temperature requirement, Onwueme (1978) stated that yams generally require temperatures in the range of 25-30 °C for normal growth. The suitability of natural climatic factors for yam production in Nigeria must have contributed to the production yams that have earned Nigeria being the largest producer of yams in the world over the years. The only improvement that makes production year round farming activity would be the introduction of irrigation.

4. Soils for Good Yam production

Ohiri and Nwokoye (1984) observed that the soil density and total porosity conducive for yam production lie within 1.10 to 1.36 g/cm³ and 46 to 56% respectively and chemically the CEC should exceed 18.0 me/100g and the level of saturation above 25%. Furthermore, exchangeable K and Mg levels should not fall below 0.3 and 2.0 me/100g soil. Abruna-Rodriguez et al., (1983) have shown that yams (*D. alata*) are very sensitive to soil acidity with yields on an ultisol decreasing from 70% of the maximum when Al saturation of ECEC of soil was 10 to 25% of maximum when Al saturation

was 40%. Yams are generally less tolerant of acidity than cassava and tanniers, hence for yams Abruna-Rodriguez (1983) recommended that soils should be limed to about pH 5.5 with essentially no exchangeable Al present whereas high yields of tanniers could be obtained at about pH 4.8 with 20% exchangeable Al and cassava could do well where pH is as low as 4.5 with up to 60% exchangeable Al. It was also inferred from the study that since maximum yam yields were obtained at pH values above 5.2, a level at which there is essentially no exchangeable Al in the soil. It follows that exchangeable Al in the main soil acidity component affecting yam yield.

Nwinyi (1981) reported that the soils of major yam growing areas range in texture from clay, sandy clay loam to sandy loam. Nwinyi also opined that the difference between soils of major and non-yam growing areas appear to be in their nutritional status especially the quantity of Ca, Mg and K which is often higher in yam producing areas. However, Carsky et al., (2010) observed further that the variability of yam yields due to chemical factors may also be attributed to differences in CEC, Mg and K contents of the soils. Obigbasan (1977) earlier indicated that N is the most limiting nutrient in root crop production though agrees that K and P may also be important, for instance, K is reputed to be responsible for the translocation of carbohydrate to storage organs. However, Asadu et al (1990) found that yams could tolerate a wide range of variation in soil

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chemical and mineralogical properties in southeastern Nigeria in prominent locations known for yam production especially under the management techniques used by the farmers but the soils of the locations best known for yam production in the zone (Zaki-Biam) were found to be moderately acid and had high base saturation with generally low CEC when compared to other soils from Abakaliliki and Atani. The ranges in soil chemical properties

obtained in yam-growing soils of southeastern Nigeria are shown in Table 3. Though the yam yields reported from all locations were high with those from the Zakibiam location topping the list (Asadu et al., 1996) soil nutrient amendments were needed to obtain the full potentials of the soils.

Table 3: Ranges in soil chemical properties tolerated by white yam (*D. rotundata*) in southeastern Nigeria

Soil property	Range
Soil pH	4.2-6.7
Soil organic matter (%)	0.31-2.41
Total N (%)	0.02-0.17
Total exchangeable acidity (me/100g soil)	0.0-4.30
Total exchangeable bases (me/100g soil)	1.27-8.76
Effective cation exchange capacity (me/100g soil)	2.14-8.83
Base saturation (%)	26.3-99.7

Source: Asadu et al., (1990).

Sobulo (1972) showed that a yam crop of 29 t/ha removed 133 kg N, 10 kg P and 85 kg K per ha and concluded that yams often responded to N sometimes to K but not to P application. One of the major problems facing yam production has been identified as that of soil fertility (Gbedolo, 1987) thus various fertilizer trails gave been carried out to help solve this problem. Baimey (2006) found that nitrogen at 160 unit per ha resulted to 18%, 25% and 21% yield increases for *D. cayenensis*, *D. dumetorum* and *D. rotundata* respectively and that potash applied at 120 and 240 unit per ha gave 13.4%

and 22.5% yield increases in *D. rotundata*. Furthermore a positive correlation between fertilizer during the peak season and economic responses to fertilizers with return/cost ratios varying between 4.8 and 7.6 was also obtained. Okoli (1973) in the work done in Northern Ghana found that K was not important in yam fertilization due to that exchangeable reserves in the soils of the area were adequate but obtained a small positive response to P applied at low level (33.6 kg/ha). This low level resulted to an average yield increase of only 5.6% obtained when the same quantity of N was

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applied. Hence N was considered the most important nutrient element in yam fertilization. From the experiments carried out at Umudike, Nigeria using NPK fertilizer mixtures, it was found that the most economic fertilizer combination for total fresh tuber yield was 67.2 kg N and 67.2 kg K per ha (Azih, 1977). This fertilizer level was also found to have no significant effect on the storage quality of the various tubers in the barn. Another trial using various nutrient combinations by Kpeglo et al (1981) indicated that *D. Rotundata* locally known as Nwopoko responded significantly to high rates of phosphorus. The trials also showed that high rates of N significantly increased the percentage of sprouting of stored tubers while increase of P and K tended to suppress sprouting and thus enhanced storability. Aduayi and Okpon (1980) also found that increased yields were obtained with increasing N fertilization particularly at the vegetative stages of growth while other elements were negatively correlated with yield at all stages of growth.

On the optimum rate and time of application of fertilizer mixtures in yam + maize + cassava crop mixtures at Umudike, Nnoke et al (1987) found that the yields of maize grain, yam tuber and cassava root increased significantly with increasing rate of fertilizer, reaching a maximum of 800 kg/ha. Although fertilizer applied at 3 weeks after planting (WAP) gave the highest yields in all cases, the differences obtained were not significant. In general for small-scale farmers of Southeastern Nigeria

that grow their yams in mixtures 800 kg/ha NPK applied at 3 WAP was recommended. Odurukwe (1986) had also shown in yam + maize mixture that fertilizer application significantly enhanced tuber yields but the component crop maize, depressed yam yield by 31%. The general trends of result of fertilizer trials tend to agree with an earlier observation made by Ferguson and Hayness (1970) that several trials using complete inorganic fertilizer though seemed to give increase in yield with fertilization, the general picture appeared to be rather confusing because of little specific information on various nutrient interactions. Similarly very often trials were conducted in areas without site (soil) characterization and specification of cultivars used. Thus, these are some of the reasons that militate against the application of most results on fertilizer trials on root and tuber crops (Howeler, 1987). Earlier study stressed that for agronomic research to be realistic and applicable to farming in tropical areas, more attention should be paid to the interplay between the variability of soil and related factors and the response of crops under different weather conditions (Moorman and Kang, 1978).

Fertilizer application in yam culture has some side effects. High rates of N combined with P resulted in substantial increases in the population of the yam nematode *Scutellonema Brady* in *D. rotundata* (Obigbesan and Adesiyin, 1981). This was not, however, the case with *D. rotundata* while phosphorous alone did not

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favour nematode build up in the tubers of the three yam varieties. Profuse weed growth is another side effect of fertilizer application. Weed control is very important in yam production. Akobundu (1980) categorically stated that at least two weeding were required for yam and cassava particularly at early stages of crop growth when leaf cover was sparse. Akobundu further observed that time spent on weeding can be up to 30% of total production time. It was found that farmers spend about 28% of their time weeding when fields were unfertilized and about 41% of their time weeding when the fields of the same sizes were fertilized (Onochie, 1975). The disadvantages of high inorganic fertilizes rates had been summarized (Fergusun and Hyness 1970) to include;

Increase in yam nematode *Scutellonema Brady*, profuse weed growth leading to farmers spending 41% of their time on fertilized as against 25% on unfertilized plots, low residual effects due to their susceptibility to leaching, high cost/non-availability and lack of recommended rate for specific areas and general site characterization.

The shape index of yam tubers defined as the ratio of length to girth of tubers was found to be affected by soil bulk density, presence or absence of rocks and root (Okoli et al, 1984). According to Ezumah (1986) the ideal conditions for the penetration and swelling of yam tubers which usually go on simultaneously

include well pulverized loose consistence, and high soil organic matter.

Climate change poses significant challenges to yam cultivation, particularly in regions like West Africa where yams are a staple food crop. Various studies have explored different adaptation strategies to mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on yam productivity (Chen and Yu, 2024). For instance, changing sowing dates has been found to be ineffective in counteracting adverse climatic effects, whereas late-maturing cultivars coupled with irrigation and fertilizer application can significantly increase yam productivity by up to 49% depending on the climate scenario (Srivastava et al., 2016). Additionally, farmers in Ebonyi State, Nigeria, have adopted mixed cropping and improved farming techniques as major adaptation strategies to cope with climate variations. In Cross River State, Nigeria, multiple cropping, crop diversification, and multiple planting dates are among the widespread adaptation practices employed by yam farmers.

Soil and water conservation are critical for sustainable yam farming, especially in the face of climate change. A transdisciplinary approach involving the development and implementation of soil and plant management technologies has shown promise in enhancing yam productivity while minimizing environmental degradation (Kiba et al., 2020). In West Africa, yam-based rotations and fertilization regimes have been identified as effective strategies to stabilize yam

production and improve water yam productivity. These practices include the use of mineral and organic fertilizers, as well as rotations with cereals and legumes (Pouya et al., 2022). Furthermore, the systematic review of climate change impacts on crops in West Africa highlights the potential of increased fertilizer use and optimized planting dates to mitigate the negative effects of climate change on crop yields (Carr et al., 2022).

The morphological soil requirement for the production of Yam including a well –drained sandy loam or loamy soils, high temperatures of 25°C–30°C, rainfall of 120 cm –180 cm per annum spread across the first six months of its growing period, abundant sunshine and pH of 4.5 –7.7 (Samaila et al., 2022). and the nutrient requirement indicate that yam respond significantly well under nitrogen and potassium fertilizer but respond slightly to phosphorus as a result of a significant removal of P by yam in the soil and partly due to the soil use for yam production are naturally rich in phosphorus (Samaila et al., 2024).

Soil quality is a critical factor in yam cultivation, influencing both yield and sustainability. In West Africa, yam is traditionally grown on nutrient-rich soils following long fallow periods, but increasing land pressure has led to soil degradation and reduced fertility (Frossard et al., 2023). Effective soil quality assessment involves evaluating soil physical, chemical, and biological properties. For instance, soil organic carbon (SOC) is a key indicator of soil health,

and its decline can significantly impact yam productivity (Liu et al., 2021). Strategies to improve soil quality include the incorporation of organic materials such as farmyard manure (FYM) and crop residues, which enhance soil structure, water retention, and nutrient availability (Brar et al., 2015). Additionally, the use of cover crops and crop rotations can improve soil organic matter and reduce erosion, further supporting sustainable yam production (Notaris et al., 2021).

5. Soil Nutrient Management Techniques

The decline in yam yields associated with loss of soil fertility has led to the conclusion that yam requires high level of nutrient for growth (O’Sullivan and Ernest, 2008). That was the major reason yam was always the first crop grown by the traditional yam farmers when a virgin forest was cleared or when the farmer returned to a fallow land in a new cycle. Nitrogen (N) and potassium (K) are largely the most important nutrients for good yam growth (Diby, 2005; O’Sullivan and Ernest, 2008)

A research conducted by Hgaza et al., (2010) on how fertilization affects yam (*D. alata* L.) growth and tuber yield for many years; revealed that fertilization significantly increased fresh tuber yield and recommended that the dose of 160 kg N ha⁻¹, 180 kg K ha⁻¹, 10 kg P ha⁻¹ and 110 kg Ca ha⁻¹ for *D. alata* production. However, Ettien et al. (2009) recommended 120 kg N ha⁻¹, 103 kg K ha⁻¹ and 38 kg P ha⁻¹ for *Dioscorea rotundata*. However, Asadu

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et al., (2008) found that 8.4 tha^{-1} fresh tuber yield obtained from application of 400 kg ha^{-1} , 15:15:15 NPK was not statistically different from 8.2 tha^{-1} from unfertilized plots because the soil had adequate nutrients that did not elicit significant yield response to mineral fertilizer application since the land was under fallow for at least 10 years before the trial was established. In order to restore or improve soil fertility and increase yam yields the introduction of legumes in the cropping system and the use of organic or mineral fertilizers had been suggested (Budelman, 1990a; Budelman, 1990b; O'Sullivan and Ernest, 2008). Budelman (1990a); reported that yam-legumes association or rotation of legumes with yams were shown to maintain or increase tuber yields in low fertility soils. The use of mineral fertilizers (mostly NPK) to improve fresh tuber yield, however, showed variable results (O'Sullivan and Ernest, 2008).

A research on the use of long yam bean (*Sphenostylis stenocarpa*) as soil amendment for the growth, leaf chemical composition and yield of white yam (*D. rotundata* L) reported increases in the yam vine length (81%), stem girth (88.4%), leaf population (69.5%), tuber weight (88.97%), tuber length (76%) and tuber girth (94%) compared to the control (Moyin-Jesu and Adekayode, 2010). The same treatment (long yam bean plants) also increased the leaf population, tuber weight, tuber length and tuber girth of yam by 11%, 31%, 30% and

55% respectively compared to NPK fertilizer treatment (Moyin-Jesu and Adekayode, 2010).

6. Fertilization and Fertilizer Requirements

Fertilization is an important management strategy in yams production especially when grown in degraded soils (Diby et al., 2011). According to Sotomayor-Ramírez et. al., (2003) a major constraint in enhancing yam productivity is low soil fertility, both in terms of macro- and micronutrient deficiencies. This is because yams are high-nutrient-demanding species and when planted in low-fertility soils under subsistence conditions as done in smallholder systems of West Africa, yields are low, varying between 9 and 10 t ha^{-1} .

Yams require high levels of soil fertility (potassium) and well-drained soils, with a pH of 6-7 (Olympio, 1982). They also need large quantities of water over a relatively long (6-10 months) growing season with the critical period between the 100th and 140th day (for late maturing cultivars) of the vegetative cycle (Osagie, 1992; Olympio, 1982). Yams do not flourish in poorly drained soils and most cultivars do not tolerate more than a few weeks of drought without significant yield losses (Osagie, 1992). The average tuber yield (12.2 Mg ha^{-1}) is low, mainly due to unscientific production practices such as relying on bush fallow practices to restore soil fertility, loss of site productivity on account of bush burning, intensive cropping often without nutrient

supplementation, overgrazing, and soil erosion as observed in Nigeria (Okonkwo, 1995).

Yam crop species and cultivars, besides site characteristics, may vary substantially in their response to fertilizer treatments (Nwinyi and Odurukwe, 1988). The higher white guinea yam yields with fertilizer application obtained (Nwinyi and Odurukwe, 1988) in their study was consistent with the findings of Yayock et al. (1988) who got yields up to 25 Mg ha⁻¹ under improved management from West Indies. Law-Ogbomo and Remison (2008) observed that the unfertilized yam plants had substantially lower leaf area index (LAI) due to fewer leaves resulting from premature leaf fall and early vine senescence and that the total plant dry weight (TDW) varied from 1.29 (unfertilized) to 3.70 t ha⁻¹ (400 kg NPK ha⁻¹) at 16 WAP which increased as the fertilizer rate increased ($r=0.64$; $p<0.05$); the dry matter accumulation increased with time and at 24 WAP, the highest values were noted for 300 kg NPK ha⁻¹ (8.77 Mg ha⁻¹). Further increases in fertilizer dose (e.g., 400 kg NPK ha⁻¹), resulted in a decline in dry matter accumulation signifying a curvilinear response pattern. According to Law-Ogbomo and Remison (2008) tuber yield per plant increased as fertilizer application increased up to 300 kg ha⁻¹, but declined thereafter (e.g., 400 kg ha⁻¹). From the study a maximum tuber yield of 24 t ha⁻¹ with application of 300 kg ha⁻¹ of NPK was obtained.

David et al., (2003) reported that in cv. Guinea Negro with micronutrient applications, the

addition of N at medium K levels (125 kg/ha) significantly increased marketable and total yields from 4,339 to 8,190 kg ha⁻¹ and 5,830 to 9,827 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. Again for cv. Guinea Negro, the highest total yields tended to result from N, P, K applications of 75, 12, 0 kg ha⁻¹, respectively, and with micronutrient additions. Similarly, Ajayi, et al., (2006) conducted a research on fertilizer treatment effects on yam (*Dioscorea* species) tuber yield in two soil types of Nigeria and reported that fertilizer treatment applications increased the yield of yam as shown in the Table 4. They also reported that residual effect of fertilizer combination application increased tuber yields of *Dioscorea* species though they were not significantly different Table 5.

The balanced use of organic and inorganic fertilizers is essential for optimizing yam yields. Research has shown that organic fertilizers, such as poultry manure and oil palm bunch ash, significantly improve soil fertility and yam growth compared to inorganic fertilizers alone (Chen and Yu, 2024). The synergistic use of organic and inorganic fertilizers can enhance nutrient availability and uptake, leading to higher tuber yields and better soil health (Zhou et al., 2022). For example, combining organic manure with NPK fertilizers has been found to increase SOC and improve soil physical properties, which are crucial for sustaining long-term productivity. Moreover, site-specific nutrient management (SSNM) practices can tailor fertilizer applications to the specific needs

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of the soil and crop, thereby maximizing efficiency and minimizing environmental impact (Shah and Wu, 2019).

Table 4: Effects of Fertilizer treatments on tuber yields of *D. Rotundata* and *D. Alata* grown in Ibadan (Rainforest agro-ecological zone and Abuja (Guinea Savanna agro-ecological zone).

Treatments	Tuber yield (t/ha)			
	D. rotundata		D. alata	
	Ibadan	Abuja	Ibadan	Abuja
Control	21.68	18.32	34.53ab	23.65
OF	20.78	17.05	37.03a	22.06
TSP	22.24	17.21	22.30b	24.75
Crystallizer	17.41	20.57	34.51ab	23.58
MOP	19.14	20.97	29.00ab	20.27
OF+TSP	18.90	19.87	40.21a	22.97
UREA	20.20	22.55	33.26ab	24.71
OF+ Crystallizer	15.42	18.48	33.56ab	26.17
OF+MOP	18.49	17.65	33.56ab	26.52
OF+TSP +MOP	16.55	17.65	35.86ab	26.67
OF+ Crystallizer + MOP	19.82	21.09	31.39ab	21.47
UREA+ TSP +MOP	23.11	19.54	35.96ab	30.27
UREA+ Crystallizer +MOP	21.06	20.41	30.52ab	25.93
LSD	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by the same letter(s) within a column are not significantly different at p = 0.05 Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT), OF = organic Fertilizer, TSP = Triple Super Sulphate, MOP = Muriate of Potash, NS = Not significant

Table 5: Residual effects of fertilizer combination on tuber yields of *D. Rotundata* and *D. Alata* grown in Ibadan (Rainforest agro-ecological zone and Abuja

Treatments	Tuber yield (t/ha)			
	D. rotundata		D. alata	
	Ibadan	Abuja	Ibadan	Abuja
Control	7.05	8.47	9.96	19.01 ab
OF	8.69	15.04	9.17	20.63 ab

TSP	10.02	17.65	12.33	22.77 ab
Crystallizer	7.32	11.00	12.49	23.38 ab
MOP	8.29	11.72	10.47	21.73 ab
OF+TSP	6.39	11.26	8.32	18.22b
UREA	6.59	12.59	14.74	27.97a
OF+ Crystallizer	9.44	11.71	14.52	22.27 ab
OF+MOP	7.65	14.78	15.09	27.83 a
OF+TSP +MOP	8.65	10.28	14.01	21.30 ab
OF+ Crystallizer + MOP	7.26	10.63	14.19	25.42 ab
UREA+ TSP +MOP	8.82	12.62	14.74	22.44 ab
UREA+ Crystallizer +MOP	8.79	10.68	14.31	23.47ab
	NS	NS	NS	

Means followed by the same letter(s) within a column are not significantly different at $p = 0.05$ Duncan Multiple Range Test (DMRT), OF = organic Fertilizer, TSP = Triple Super Sulphate, MOP = Muriate of Potash, NS = Not significant

7. Fertilizer Recommendations for Individual Yam Species

Response to fertilizers depends mainly on the native fertility of the soil as well as the variety in cultivation. In traditional bush fallow agriculture in West Africa, yams were usually

grown during the first season after clearance from bush, thus obtaining reasonably good yields without using fertilizer. However, as land scarcity resulted in shorter fallow period and yields decreased progressively, traditional farmers would need less persuasion to use fertilizer on their yams. From different trials the nutrients removed from soils by different varieties of yam are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Nutrient demand/uptake/removal by different varieties of yam

Species	Tuber yield t/ha	Source	Macronutrients (kg/ha)						
			N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	MgO	CaO	S	
D. alata (Greater yam)	35.95	Obigbesan and Agboola (1978)	128.5	38.9	195.0	18.7	5.6	-	
	18.60	Kabeerathumma al., (1987)	75.0	21.3	108.8	6.5	16.3	-	

D. rotundata (White yam)	26.90	Sobulo (1972)	205.0	29.8	135.0	-	-	-
	51.60	Irizarry and Rivera, (1985)	189.0	57.3	259.0	61.0	127.4	-
	30.00	Kabeerathumma et al, (1987)	91.2	34.4	124.9	9.8	25.8	-
	37.90	Obigbesan and Obigbesan (1978)	148.0	41.2	199.2	18.6	5.6	-
D. cayenensis (Yellow yam)	45.13	Obigbesan and Agboola (1978)	139.0	43.5	218.0	22.0	5.6	-
D. esculenta (Lesser yam)	17.87	Kabeerathumma et al, (1987)	73.0	25.8	77.3	10.5	19.8	-

Micronutrients (g/ha)

			Fe	Mn	Zn	Cu
D. alata (Greater yam)	18.60	Kabeerathumma et al, (1987)	1 400	180	134	157
D. rotundata (White yam)	30.00	Kabeerathumma et al, (1987)	3 000	334	290	267
D. esculenta (Lesser yam)	17.87	Kabeerathumma et al, (1987)	2 000	320	280	114

Fertilizer recommendations for individual yam species as reported in different regions are shown in Table 7. The soil types are also mentioned, thus site specific trials are needed in dominant soil areas growing yams in the world

for mineral fertilizer requirements for optimum yam production.

Table 7: Fertilizer recommendations for individual yam species

Macronutrients (kg/ha)

Dioscorea esculenta	N	P ₂ O ₅	MgO
(medium yield 15-20 t/ha, Kerala, India)			-
On lateritic sandy clay loam (ultisol)			
Within 1 week after sprouting	40	60	-
One month later	40		
On forest soil rich in organic matter:			-
Within 1 week after sprouting	30	60	
One month later	30		-
Dioscorea alata			
(medium yield 12 1/2-25 t/ha, Kerala, India)			
On lateritic sandy clay loam (ultisol):			
Within 1 week after sprouting	40	60	-
One month later	40		-
(high yield > 25 t/ha, Puerto Rico)	500	kg/ha 10:10:10	mixture
		containing 30 kg/t of a mixture of 6 % Mg, 7.7 % Mn, 4.8 % Cu, 7 % Fe, 8 % Zn and 2.5 % B.	
On acid corozal clay soil (aquic tropodults), limed to pH > 5.5:	500	kg/ha of same mixture	
At planting	500	kg/ha of same mixture	
After 5 months			
Dioscorea rotundata			
(low yield < 15 t/ha, Nigeria)			
On gravelly sandy loam:	-	13	-
At planting	30	-	-
4 weeks after planting	30	-	-
10 weeks after planting	35	25	-
On light loamy ultisol:			
8 weeks after planting	40	60	
(medium yield 25-30 t/ha, Kerala, India)	40	-	-
On lateritic sandy clay loam (ultisol):			-
Within 1 week after sprouting	112	34	
One month later	112	34	

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(high yield > 30 t/ha, Puerto Rico)

On Corozal clay soil (ultisol):

			28
2 months after planting	102	34	28
5 months after planting	102	-	

On lateritic sandy clay loam (ultisol):

2 weeks after germination	50	50	-
1 month later	50	-	-

2 weeks after germination

1 month later

Source: Kabeerathumma et al., (1987).

8. Plant Population and Sett Weight

In Nigeria plant population of 10,000 to 15,000 per hectare gave the highest yields depending on the variety (Baker, 1964). However, increasing plant population from 9,000 to 36,000 plants per hectare increased yields linearly but decreased average tuber weight while the number of tubers per plant was not affected (Gurmah, 1974). Furthermore, increasing sett weight from 203 to 608 g increased yields per hectare as well as the number of tubers per plant but average tuber weight was not affected.

In Nigeria the production of ware yams (large tubers for consumption) requires the use of sizeable yam setts. According to Nwoke et al., (1973) the main effect of large sett size is to produce a vigorous initial growth of root, vine and leaves which give the plant an advantage that lasts throughout the growing season. Ferguson (1973) finds that in white Lisbon yam, large setts emerge earlier, produce larger primary nodal complexes and greater leaf area, began rapid tuber bulking earlier and had longer duration of tuber bulking. The larger

primary nodal complexes and greater leaf area may be due to greater food reserves in larger tubers that are translocated to the early sprouts for metabolic purposes (Adesuyi, 1977). This diversion of nutrients according to Nwoke and Okonkwo (1978) even takes place pre-emergence and such initial advantages are maintained through the life of the plant, thus leading to higher yields.

The density of plant population tends to affect the size of seed yams to be used. Baker (1964) reports a linear increase in yield and a decrease in mean germination when sett size increases from 50 to 250g. Baker also states that in Nigeria plant population of 10,000 to 15,000 per hectare gave the highest yields depending on the variety. According to Gurmah (1974) increasing plant population from 9,000 to 36,000 plants per hectare increased yields linearly but decreased average tuber weight while the number of tubers per plant was not affected. Gurmah further notes that increasing sett weight from 203 to 608g increased yields per hectare as well as the number of tubers per plant but average tuber weight was not affected.

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The main effect of large sett size is to produce a vigorous initial growth of root, vine and leaves which give the plant an advantage that lasts throughout the growing season (Nwoke et al., 1973). The field trials by Obigbesan (1980) on the Chinese yam (*D. esculenta*) showed that crop yield was predominantly determined by the size of seed-tuber planted. It was thus recommended as a practical guide that farmers plant seed-tubers of 100-150g while small size tubers should be used for seed multiplication. Lyonga and Ayuk-Takem (1982) recommended 375-500 g as optimum sett weight for ware yam production and 125 g for seed yam production with a population density of 15 000 per ha as the most economical. Similarly, Enyi (1973) found that the yields of *D. esculenta* (Lesser yam) increased with increase in seed size and attributed the results to increasing tuber number, leaf area duration and bulking rate. From the study, tuber yield was highly and positively significantly correlated with leaf area duration and increased leaf area was also correlated with increased vine growth. Similarly the study revealed that increase in plant density led to an increase in tuber yield, relative leaf area duration and mean bulking rate per ha.

Onwueme (1975) observed that some setts of *D. rotundata* placed in moist sawdust produced new tubers without their shoots emerging above the dust and suggested that this could offer a partial explanation for the greatest tuber yield that results from larger setts because the photosynthate in the sett was being transferred

into the new tuber. Ebong (1987) found that seed factor ratios were relatively higher for sett weights in the range 100 to 300g than those in the range 400 to 600 g. Significant correlation was found between fresh tuber yields per plant and number of tubers per plant, length of tuber, circumference of tubers and weight of tubers. From the study it was noted that in selecting for higher tuber yield per plant, greater progress would be made if selection was done on plants with fewer tubers per plant and raised from smaller seed setts.

It has been confirmed, under experimental conditions, that the greater the weight of the sett used to establish the yam plant, the greater the weight of seed tuber produced from the plant (Igbokwe et al., 1982; Gurnah, 2008; Okoli and Opara, 1987; Eke-Okoro et al., 2008). Udealor and Ezulike (2009) reported that total yield of seed yam yield significantly increased with increase in sett size. Seed yam yield from 35g and 45 g were not significantly different but were each significantly different from that of 25g.

They observed that the yield and number of seed yams above 500g obtained from 35g and 45g sett sizes were not significantly different and therefore recommend the use of minisetts size of 35g for seed yam production above 500g in order to produce fat ware yams (4-5kg). According to Okoli et al., (1982) the recommendation of 25g sett size is still valid for farmers who want to produce seed yams below 500g which will produce a less ware yam.

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Ikeh et al., (2012) evaluated the yield productivity and economic returns of some yam (*D. esculenta* Poir) genotypes grown in a kaolinitic ultisol and reported that the yield and yield components of the yam genotypes considered (TDr 95/18894, TDr 99/AMO/094 and local variety- Eteme) varied significantly in number of seed and ware tubers per plant in 2008 and 2009 cropping seasons. According to them TDr 95/18894 produced the highest number of seed and ware tubers per plant, 4.31 and 2.36 in 2008 and 4.33 and 2.41 in 2009 respectively, followed by TDr 99/AMO/094, 3.30 and 2.33 in 2008 and 3.31 and 2.34 in 2009, respectively. While the local variety, Eteme, on the average had the least number of seed and ware tubers, 2.03 and 0.00 in 2008 and 2.30 and 1.00 in 2009 respectively. The TDr 95/18894 produced 23-53% and 23-47% more number of seed tubers than other genotypes in 2008 and 2009, respectively. It also had 1-100 and 3-75% more ware tubers than other yam genotypes.

The seed and ware tuber yields also indicated significant differences (Table 2), TDr 95/18894 genotype also maintained superiority in seed and ware tuber yields, 20.11 and 7.63 (t/ha) in 2008 and 22.26 and 8.75 (t/ha) of seed and ware tuber yield in 2009, respectively. Similarly, comparing the total tuber (seed and ware) yield, TDr 95/18894 genotypes produced the highest in both cropping seasons, 27.74 and 31.01 t/ha, respectively, followed by 99/AMO/094, 26.83 and 27.30 t/ha in 2008

and 2009, respectively, TDr 99/AMO/053, 26.63 t/ha in 2008 and M2/50/5x, 27.26 t/ha in 2009. The least total tuber yield in both cropping years was obtained from local genotype (Eteme), 10.13 and 13.16 t/ha in 2008 and 2009 respectively.

The performance of yam could also be affected by the portion of the tuber planted. Asadu and Akamigbo (1996) obtained significantly higher increase in the yield of *D. rotundata* when top portions (proximal end) of the tuber was used than when middle or tail portions were used. The yields from the tail end position were higher than that from the middle portion but the difference was not significant. The better performance of the top portion was attributed to the early sprouting and establishment of the plants emerging from top portion of the tuber. However, Passam (1982) later found that sprout emergence in *D. alata* tuber was independent of tuber part nor storage time.

In India the yields of *D. floribunda* was found to be higher if grown for a period of two years using the middle and tip, portions of the tuber as planting materials (Rao et al., 1978). According to Degras (1975) the origin of the mother tuber of *D. trifida* affected the early growth and development while senescence of foliage was more affected by environmental conditions.

According to Onwueme (1978) yams are generally grown in mounds because of the following advantages:

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-provision of loose seed-bed for tuber penetration,

-collection of fertile soil from surrounding area of the mounds,

-for water control in areas with high water table, and

-to facilitate harvesting.

The size of mounds used was found to vary according to soil type and depth to water table (Torto, 1956). Mound size was found to have more pronounced effect on tuber yield than even fertilizer thus; planting on large mounds also resulted to longer tubers and shorter harvesting time (Kang and Wilson, 1981).

In Barbados land for planting yams is prepared by harrowing in the cane residues, subsoiling and ridging at intervals of 1.7 m and planting was normally done by hand along the top of the ridges at 0.7 to 1.0 m intervals (Gooding, 1970). Planting on ridges or flat seed-bed in Cameroon gave no significant difference in tuber yields but yams from flat seed-beds had more defective tubers and poorer shape (Lyonga and Ayuk-Takem, 1982). Ebong (1987), however, found that yields per plant were significantly higher from mounds and ridges than from flats, holes or trenches. Hulugalle et al (1985) also found that depth of rooting and yield of yam were significantly improved by tillage in combination with mulching. Their result showed that tuber yield increased from 9.8 t ha⁻¹ from no-till no-mulch to 13.9 t ha⁻¹ for conventional tillage with mulching.

Mulching of yams fields according to Lal (1975) decreased the period from planting to emergence, increased the percentage emergence, growing period as well as tuber yield. Okoli et al., (1986) showed that plastic mulch with stakes, gave 68 to 80% greater yield of ware yams when compared with no mulching. Staking yam vines alone increased yield by 20% compared to no staking while plastic mulch alone with no staking gave a 39% more yield compared to the traditional system. On the effects of different mulching materials and plant population on the performance of yam miniset, Okoh (2024) found that tuber size and total tuber yield were larger by over 50% using the white plastic mulch than in the traditional staking method and more than double those in the no-mulch, no-staking treatment. The proportion of total tuber yield of marketable size (>200 g) was similarly higher under the white plastic mulch. For both varieties of yams tested, tuber size decreased with increasing plant density with or without mulching. However, differences between mulched and unmulched treatments were generally larger at lower plant population indicating reduced benefits from mulching at higher plant densities. Plants with the white plastic mulch maintained a higher leaf area index for most of the growing season as well as longer leaf duration.

Ogbonna et al., (2011) researched on the profitability of minituber seed yam production technique in South east agro-ecological zone

using three white yam varieties TDr89/02677, TDr89/02665 and TDr89/02565 known for their high potential yield. They reported that TDr89/02677 had the highest yield 13.84 t/ha; 8.71 t/ha for 2008 and 2009 respectively and giving a mean yield of 11.28 t/ha. This was followed by TDr89/02665, 9.32 t/ha; 8.68 t/ha for 2008 and 2009 respectively with a mean yield of 9.06 t/ha while TDr89/02565 had the least yield 12.72 t/ha; 5.10 t/ha 2008 and 2009 respectively with a mean yield of 8.91 t/ha.

9. Intercropping/Mixed Cropping

The advantages of intercropping/mixed cropping systems are well known including insurance against total crop failure occasioned by sudden changes in climatic elements especially rainfall, pest insurgence among others (Asadu,2016; Asadu, 2025). Yam and maize are Nigeria's leading crops both in terms of land under cultivation and preferred major staple food crops contributing immensely to rural and regional economies apart from cassava, and maize and cassava are the most popular arable crops intercropped with yam in yam-based cropping systems in Nigeria (Asadu, 1997; Agboola, 2000). A research work on the productivity of yam-minisetts as influenced by maize introduction dates showed that delaying the time of maize introduction did not improve yam-minisett tuber yield (Madu and Nwosu, 2001). The effect of time of introducing maize on the yield of white guinea yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* P.) mini-setts in Makurdi showed that the greatest number of tubers, tuber weight

per plant and tuber yield were obtained from yam-minisett planted at same time as maize and the yield was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) greater by 17.2 % and 31.0 % respectively, compared to that obtained from yam-minisett that had maize introduced at 3 and 6 weeks later in 2023 (Ijoyah, 2010). Similarly, in 2004, tuber yield obtained from yam-minisett planted at same time as maize was significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) greater by 9.5 % and 19.7 % respectively, compared to that obtained from yam-minisett that had maize introduced at 3 and 6 weeks later. Ano et al., (2003) reported the contribution of leguminous crops to nutrient availability and productivity of yam based systems. They reported the highest yam minisett yield (t/ha) of 4.70 from yam minisett/pigeon pea and 4.67 from sole yam minisett; 3.84 from yam minisett /Ground nut; 3.41 from yam minisett /Bambara nut. According to their report yam minisett/pigeon pea contributed the highest percentage soil organic matter of 3.55% and sole yam minisett the least, 2.90% while yam minisett/Ground nut and yam minisett /Bambara nut contributed 3.05% and 2.95% respectively. Yam minisett/pigeon pea produced the highest weight of legume haulm of 4.57t/ha at legume harvest followed by yam minisett /ground nut (3.94t/ha) and yam minisett /Bambara nut (0.54t/ha).

In yam-based cropping system in south-eastern Nigeria, the best period for introducing cassava, based on yields and estimated revenue from both crops, was between two and three months

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after the planting of yams in April and after mound-remoulding (collecting soil between the mounds and placing it around the mounds using local hoes) and this practice reduced the number of times weeding was required from three to one, and reduced erosion by improving the infiltration capacity of the yam mounds, since the soil material used in remoulding was often loose. The thin layer of earth on the mound after remoulding served as an earth mulch which covers yam roots often exposed by the torrential rainfall characteristic of the area (Asadu, 1997).

Intercropping systems, such as yam-fluted pumpkin/melon-okra/maize, have been shown to reduce weed growth and increase the yield of component crops, highlighting the importance of selecting compatible intercrop combinations for better resource utilization (Weerarathne et al., 2017). Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, which include reduced tillage and residue retention, have been found to improve soil microclimate and nutrient uptake, further supporting the need for optimal plant density and spacing (Remya and Suja, 2023).

10. Weed, Pests and Diseases

Weeds, pests and diseases as important constraints on yam production have attracted various research interests. According to Akobundu (1980) the climbing habit of white yam (*D. rotundata*) coupled with its inability to shade the ground completely at any stage of its growth and development made it very susceptible to weed interferences and this was

found to affect the yield. Galinato and Sajise (1981) identified the major weed species in yam field in the Philippines as *Cyperus rotundus*, *Paspalum conjugatum*, *Ageratina adenophora*, *Pennisetum polystachyon*, *Digitaria sanguinalis*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, *Eragrostis tenalla* and *Desmodium triflorum*. According to Unamma et al., (1981) when a solution released from weed roots came into contact with the soil in which yams were grown tuber yield was significantly reduced, suggesting allelopathy. Thus, weed interference during the vegetative and tuber bulking stages of white yam were thought to affect assimilate production. Unamma et al. (1981) also found that weeds often competed with yams for N, P, and water and also introduced allelochemicals into the crop environment which significantly accentuated the crop yield depression.

Orkwor (1990) reported that uncontrolled weeds reduced yields of yam tubers by 35% and that yam has a critical weed free requirement period of 16 weeks both in sole cropping as well as in intercropping.

A lot of farmer's time is spent on weeding and it has been reported that up to 32.4% (including land clearing) and 28.0 % {excluding land clearing} of farmer's time could be spent on weeding in yam fields in Western Nigeria (Anon., 1972).

Several weed control measures such as biological, cultural and chemical methods have been researched into, so as to find best alternatives. When Akobundu (1980) compared

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weed suppression by low-growing crops with other methods of weed control at high rainfall (200 cm/year) and medium rainfall (130 cm/year), it was found that melon (*Citrullus lanatus*) sown in the beginning of the season, followed by sweet potato (*Ipomea batatas*) cuttings gave better maize and yam yields than for hand-weeding or application of primextra herbicide. The time of weeding also found to be important because according to Beale (1983), in Puerto Rico, hand weeding conducted for more than 2.5 months of crop growth did not significantly decrease yield but the data obtained from the study suggested that the critical period for maintaining yams fields weed free is between 2.5 and 4.0 months after planting. Onwueme and Fadayomi (1980) compared the conventional staked, hand-weeded yam production, and a new production package in which the yams were not staked and weeds were controlled with ametryne (4 kg/ha) + paraquat (1kg/ha) applied at or just before emergence and found that when small (150g) setts were used, yields from the new package were not significantly lower than those from the conventional system, even though the new package was considerably less laborious. Cultivation with large setts, however, resulted in a decrease in yield when the plants were not staked.

In Soviet Far East, Ivashenko (1975) reported that urea herbicide gave good weed control in *D. nipponica* and had no residues in the roots nor was the saponin content of the crop

reduced. The persistence of the herbicides in the soil was considered important and Unamma and Akobundu (1989) found that atrazin and metolachlor were less persistent in soil than fluometuron and pendimethalio.

Pests are known to cause severe damage to yams both in the field and storage facilities as Ebenebe, 1977; Korada, et al., 2010; and Palanis-wami et al, 1982) had reported that many pests attack yams and even those known to attack other crops now devour yams. Lal and Pillai (1977) reported severe damage to *D. rotundata* and *D. alata* at the time of harvest attributed to the white grubs which gouge shallow and irregular but mostly circular pits in the yams. A mealy bug identified as *Rhizoecus angustus* James. (Ebenebe, 1977) was found to damage yams in Wusasa, Northern Nigeria. The pest was previously found on a medicinal need *Leonotis nepetalifolia* and on a fodder grass in Kenya. USDA (1978) reported that a new pest (*Aspidiotus destructor*) which used to attack coconut in Hawaii was found to infest yam (*Dioscorea* spp.) at Pearl City on the Island of Oahu. Palaniswami et al (1982) reported that the mealy bug, *Ferrisia virgate* originally known to be a serious pest of jute now attacks, *Dioscorea dumentorum* causing severe damage in India. According to Williams, (1994) the principal enemy of most yam species in French West Indies is cassava ant (*Acromyrmex octospinosus* Reich). A control device for this pest involves placing at the entrance of the ant heap a bait poisoned with Mirex 459.

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Yams in storage are also attacked by many pests which in fact contribute to the low shelf life of yams. A study by Plumbley and Press (1983) in Southeastern Nigeria indicated yams in storage were infested by two yam pest species namely *Araecerus fasciculatus* and *Decadarchios miruscula*. The two pests were found together on the yams and mainly attacked cut and damaged areas of the stored tubers. Again Osuji (1980) surveyed beetles that attack dried yams in Nigerian market and recorded ten different species with *Dinoderus porcellus* Lesne as the most abundant and the cigarette beetle, *Lasioderma serricornis* Fab as a potentially important pest species of the products examined.

Acosta and Ayala (1976) reported that *Pratylenchus coffeae* (nematode) was responsible for most of the storage rot deterioration and dry rot of yam in Puerto Rico. Adesiyun and Odihirin (1977) observed that both dry rot and wet rot diseases were found in all the yam barns and market visited in Midwest Nigeria. Galled tubers caused by root-knot nematode were found to be more common with *D. alata*. For the control of nematodes, Acosta and Ayala (1976) found that the number of *Pratylenchus coffeae* was reduced greatly by hot water dips and immersion of tubers in Nemagon solutions or in Dasanit or Nemaphos and this gave a good control of the nematodes without affecting tuber germination. Similarly drying of tubers of *D. alata* infested by the nematode *Scutellinia Brady* in hot water

completely suppressed the nematode without adversely affecting the storage life, germination, growth and yield of the tubers (Adeniji, 1977). It was reported (Badra and Caveness, 1979) that seed pieces of *D. alata* treated with formalin, carbofuran and D-D against *S. Brady* gave the greatest yield. Roman et al (1984) evaluated three nematicides for nematode control in Puerto Rico and found that aldicarb was more effective than carbofuran and fensulfotion. The result also showed that the use of highly effective non-volatile nematicides if registered for their use in yam could help in reducing the annual crop losses caused by the nematode *Pratylenchus coffeae*.

The diseases of yam both in the field and in store may also be caused by bacteria, fungi or virus. Arene et al. (1985) identified two phases involved in yam tuber pathology as tuber/soil or rhizosphere phase and the post harvest phase. The interplay between host metabolites and the pathogen enzyme was understood to involve polyphenols and phytoalexins from the host and cellulytic and pectolytic enzymes from the pathogen. A lot of yield losses due to anthracnose in *D. alata* have been reported (Unamma and Akobundu, 1989)). Anthracnose and scorch were found to cause general necrosis of the leaves and vines which are responsible for heavy yield losses. Amusa et al., (2003) indicated that *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides* Penzig, which caused yam anthracnose, was found to survive in infested host debris left on the field or ploughed under as well as in infected tubers,

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diseased stubble attached to the tubers and in soil. These, therefore, were found to constitute the sources of the primary inoculums of the disease. The study also showed that the treatment of the diseased setts with fungicide prior to planting reduced primary infection and the incidence of leaf infection, and vine die tuck were significantly reduced by the foliar application of benomyl.

A virus diseases of white yam (*D. rotundata* Poir) in Nigeria characterized by severe green vein-banding and mottling of the foliage had long been detected in four states in Nigeria; Oyo, Kwara, Edo and Niger with Edo having the highest incidence and Niger the lowest (Mohammed and Terry, 1979). In Carribeans, Eni (2008) found three types of virus namely flexuous rods, baciliform and isometric types to be associated with substantial economic loss of yams in the region. The use of disease free tubers is regarded as the only best method for the control of the virus diseases since the diseases are perpetuated from year to year through infected planting materials.

Leaf sport has been considered as a serious disease of *D. dumetorum* (Emua and Fajola, 1981) with symptoms occurring four days after inoculation and sporulation two days later. Out of the five fungicides tested for the control of the disease, mancozeb was recommended for field use because of its effectiveness, low phytotoxicity, low cost and the apparent luxuriant growth it produced in treated plants. Sharma (1984) tested 19 fungicides for the

control of tuber rot caused by *Fusarium solani* and found that bavistin, benomyl, karathane and griseofulium showed complete inhibition of the growth of the pathogen at 50 µg/ml in vitro. In another experiment (in viro) it was observed that 1000 and 2000 µg/ml of benomyl and baristin were effective in controlling the disease when used as post inoculation treatment. Fungicide treatment of seed pieces of *D. rotundata* cv Habanero has been found to be very important even with good seed pieces and well prepared seedbeds (Mignucci et al.; 1984). For early and greater emergence of seed pieces which in turn appear to be important determinants of yield and tuber size in Habanero yams fungicide treatment is necessary. Without fungicide treatments yield could diminish by as much as one half. Egesi et al., (2009) reported that yam anthracnose and virus diseases are the most important biotic constraints affecting yam production in the world. From the study it was found that environment, genotype and genotype by environment contributed 26%, 48% and 25.9% respectively in the spread of anthracnose disease of yam, signifying that environment and genotype were very important in the spread of yam anthracnose. Again from the same study it was also reported that environment, genotype and genotype by environment contributed 5.67%, 75.4% and 18.9% respectively in the spread of virus diseases of yam meaning that genotype plays vital role in the spread and control of viral diseases of yam.

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According to FAO (2012), yam is the most valuable staple crop in Côte d'Ivoire, with over 7.2 million tonnes produced in 2018. It is reported that *D. rotundata* accounts for 75% of the yam trade in the country. Because yams are vegetatively propagated, the primary means of easily spreading plant diseases, particularly viruses, is through infected propagules. The endemic activities of these yam viruses result in “after effects” such as reduced quality of harvested tubers and gross yield losses. It is noteworthy that insect vectors, including aphids (vectors for YMV and CMV) and mealybugs (vectors for Badnavirus), have been shown to facilitate the activities and spread of yam viruses through mechanical transmission in a non/semi-persistent manner (Thouvenel et al., 1990; Odu et al., 1999; Phillips et al., 1999; Odu et al., 2004). In contrast to other pests and pathogens, including nematodes, bacteria, fungi, and insects, yam viruses are also the hardest to control. In general, colossal losses have been documented on *D. rotundata*, specifically due to the devastating impact of YMV (Adeniji et al., 2012). This grim reality is typically due to the combined effects of biotic and abiotic forces.

The diagnostic methods for identifying yam viruses in *D. rotundata* have gained significant attention, regardless of the valuable information that may be gleaned from symptom manifestations alone. The sensitivity,

specificity, speed, ease of use, reliability, reproducibility, and even price of these diagnostics are crucial indicators that may help in selecting the most appropriate technique in a certain circumstance. To achieve the best study results, these techniques could be applied separately or in combination, as in the case of Immunocapture-PCR (IC-PCR). In this succinct review, molecular-based and serological methods will be discussed.

In West Africa, many viruses have been routinely indexed and shown to cause either moderate or severe infections in yams. These viruses include the following: potyviruses (yam mosaic virus, YMV, and yam mild mosaic virus, YMMV), cucumoviruses (cucumber mosaic virus, CMV), badnaviruses (*Dioscorea alata* bacilliform virus), potexviruses (*Dioscorea* latent virus), and sadwaviruses (*Dioscorea* mosaic-associated virus, DMaV). Consequently, yam growers in Nigeria and Côte d'Ivoire have reported disastrous crop losses. Common viral symptoms were also noted, including mosaic, leaf distortion, leaf banding, interveinal chlorosis, necrosis, puckering, mottling, stunted growth, and brown spots on the leaves (Bakayoko et al., 2021b; Eni et al., 2008; Odedara et al., 2012; Odu et al., 2004; Séka et al., 2009; Silva et al., 2015; Toualy et al., 2014). Figure 2 shows typical virus symptoms on yam.

Figure 2. Typical virus symptoms on yam, (A) *D. rotundata* TDr 99/02674 showing mosaic symptoms; (B) *D. rotundata* cv. Adaka showing chlorotic leaf discoloration, and (C) mottling; (D) *D. rotundata* TDr 00/00168 showing leaf deformation ((A–D) source: Silva (2019)); (E) *D. rotundata* leaf discoloration (Source: Omeonu et al., 2025) (F) *D. alata* showing diffused mottling.

For example, yam virus symptoms in *D. rotundata* were reported in Nigeria (Jonathan, 2019). Aside from the reduction in the photosynthetic activity of the infected plant and the evident yield losses triggered by these symptoms, the plant may eventually die (Odu et al., 2001).

There are currently 25 viruses that infect yams, according to the International Committee for the Taxonomy of Viruses (ICTV). These viruses

are classified into eight families (Alphaflexiviridae, Betaflexiviridae, Bromoviridae, Caulimoviridae, Closteroviridae, Potyviridae, Secoviridae, and Tombusviridae) and twelve genera (Aureusvirus, Ampelovirus, Badnavirus, Carlavirus, Cucumovirus, Dioscavirus, Fabavirus, Macluravirus, Potexvirus, Potyvirus, Sadwavirus, and Velarivirus) (Silva et al., 2019).

Broadly, the diversity of viruses that affect yam, especially *D. rotundata*, is largely determined by several key factors. These factors comprise yam varieties, vector transmission mechanisms, host range, environmental influences, virus evolution, agricultural practices, co-infection with numerous viruses, climatic change, etc. Molecular characterization studies demonstrate that these variables contribute to the rapid evolution of yam viruses, such as YMV, YMMV,

and Badnaviruses, into new pathogenic strains in different genotypes of *D. rotundata*.

The cultivation of *Dioscorea rotundata* is significantly threatened by the yam mosaic virus (Mignouna et al., 2001). It is a viral disease that results in the formation of unique mosaic patterns on the leaves of yam plants. This leads to a decrease in the plant's ability to carry out photosynthesis, resulting in stunted growth and reduced output of yam tubers.

Effective pest, disease, and weed management strategies are essential for sustainable yam production. The use of pesticides and neem leaf powder has been effective in managing plant parasitic nematodes and reducing tuber galling, leading to higher yields. Integrated weed management (IWM) strategies, including intercropping and the use of ground cover mulches, have been shown to significantly reduce weed biomass and improve crop yields (Nedunchezhiyan et al., 2018). Conservation chemical practices have also been effective in reducing weed density and biomass, while improving soil quality and microbial activities. These strategies are vital for addressing the challenges of soil fertility, pest pressure, and weed infestation in yam cultivation.

11. Processing/Composition and Storage

The area of yam processing has attracted limited research interests for now. The three problems identified by Ngoddy and Onuoha (1983) in the processing of instant yam flour included development of colour resulting from enzymatic browning mediated by polyphenol

oxidase, rheology and texture of acceptable pounded yam, slow and energy intensive nature of drying pregelled yam pieces. Peoples' taste is also important while considering yam processing, for instance, a study of flakes prepared from pre-cooked paste from tubers of six varieties showed that for the West Indian market, where a fluffy texture is required, only *D. alata*, 'Lisbon', 'coconut' and oriental cultivars may be used for the production of flakes, while where a sticky texture is required as in Africa, *D. rotundata* and *D. trifida* may be used (Steele and Sammy, 1976). In Barbados a unique method of processing is used (Campbell and Gooding (1962). In this process the tubers are cooked, mashed and drum dried after being rolled into a thin film. This is then broken and packaged for sale. This has been test-marketed in Europe, North America and the Caribbean with fair success (Campbell and Gooding (1962).

In processing generally, Ayernor (1976) considered two important variables namely tissue cooking and comminution condition. It was found that modules of elasticity, ultimate deformation, recoverable elasticity and energy loss ratio of the various samples were related to the degree of starch damage. To improve on yam flour quality, Collins and Falasinnu (1977) fortified yam flour with soy flour, rehydrated it to a doughy consistence and tested for resistance to extrusion, colour and preference. It was found that the food product was similar to pounded yam 'fufu' popularly eaten in West

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Africa but there was reduced consistency and increased strictness. The protein content was raised from 1.25% to between 5 and 10%. For the preservation of the nutrient contents of yams *D. dumetorum*, *D. rotundata*, *D. cayenensis* and *D. schinperaria*, during traditional processing, Bell and Favier (1981) showed that cooking in boiling water with the peel and frying are the processes that preserve the main nutrients. Due to the low protein contents of most root and tuber crops, they are often, considered inadequate sources of protein in the diet when compared to grain staples but according to Coursey (1967) this should be considered only true for cassava not yams or aroids because some yams contain 6% or more protein. Thus if the utilizable protein value is considered yam may be only marginally inferior to maize and rice, the major tropical grain staples. Coursey thus noted that yam-based diets, therefore, need relatively little supplementation with high grade protein compared, say, with cassava or plantain based diets. Exceptions are, however, made for food for young children, pregnant or lactating women who have higher protein requirements.

Baquar and Oke (1976) have shown that some clones of *D. alata* and *D. dumetorum* have protein content of between 3.2 and 13.9% dry weight, hence they are superior to some maize and rice varieties in usable proteins. For all minerals except Ca, yams on the average are richer than cassava, cocoyams and potatoes (Elkims, 1979) but Egbe and Treche (1984)

noted the variability in the chemical composition of yam tuber even within the same cultivar depending in the prevailing environmental condition from which they were produced.

The results of various works on the composition of yam varieties have been summarized by Eka (1985). From the study the moisture content ranged from 60 to 85%, dry mater from 7-40% ether extract 0.04 to 2.0% (dry weight basis) and from 0.05 to 0.3% (wet weight basis). In general the peels tended to be higher in crude fibre than unpeeled tuber and also richer in total ash than the unpeeled and peeled tubers. The proximate composition of yam showed that yams are rich in thiamin, riboflavin, niacin and ascorbic acid and the thiamin content ranged from 50 to 150 μg per 100 edible portion, riboflavin from 20 to 101 μg , niacin from 300 to 2,200 μg and ascorbic acid from 200 to 21, 000 μg while *D. dumetorum* was found to be richer in most of the vitamins than other varieties and the limiting essential amino acids in yams were the sulfur containing amino acids (Eka, 1985).

Yam tubers have also been reported to contain some toxicants and anti-nutritional compounds (Shajeela et al., 2011; Martin, 1979). The interest of nutritionists had been oxalic acid, phytic acid, pydrocyamic acid and tannins. All yams contain oxalic acid but the level of soluble oxalate which was known to be toxic to man and animal was not high and ranged from 5.3 to 11.6 mg/100g dry sample. The lethal dose of soluble oxalate for man was reported to range from 2 to

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7 g and the methods of preparation of yam tubers for consumption also tended to reduce the level of soluble oxalate (Martin, 1979) The characteristic composition of three varieties of yams in Table 8 show that they contain over 50% water, over 15% carbohydrate and starch, and some minerals and vitamin C ((Baah, 2009))

Table 8: Some Dioscorea yam species and their nutrient value per 100g fresh edible tube portions

Source: Baah (2009).

Mentin (1982) found that the level of phytic acid in yam tubers ranged from 3.7 to 9.7 mg/100g dry matter while the level of hydrocyanic acid arising presumably from the cyanogenic glycosides found in tubers ranged from 1.0 mg to 1.89 mg/100 dry matter but these levels may not constitute dangers to those

that consume yams especially if cooked yams are consumed. Some toxicants reported to be present in yams by Martin (1979) include calcium oxalate crystals, tannins, alkaloids and steroidal sapogenins and the poisonous substances responsible for the bitterness in *D. bulbifera* were identified as furanoid and diterpene.

Some pharmacologically active substances reported in yam tubers are discorine, saponins and sapogenins. Martin (1979) reported the presence of dioscorine in *D. bulbifera* and the uses include as a paste in healing swellings and as a cure for snake bite (India), treatment of scorpion stings and ulcers (Jamaica) as well as a stimulant for excessive drinking (Africa). The foaming properties of saponins make them useful for washing purposes, as shampoo, and as a foaming agent in fire extinguishers. From

Nutrient (g/100g)	<i>D. alata</i> (water yam)	<i>D. rotundata</i> (white yam)	<i>D. cayenensis</i> (yellow yam)
% Moisture	65-78.6	50.0-80	60-84
% Carbohydrate	22-31	15-23	16
% Starch	16.7-28	26.8-32.2	16.0
% Free sugar	0.5-1.4	0.3-1	0.4
% Free sugar	1.1-3.1	1.1-2.3	1.1-1.5
% Crude fat	<0.1-0.6	0.05-0.1	0.06-0.2
% Fibre	1.4-3.8	1.0-1.7	0.4
% Ash	0.7-2.1	0.7-2.6	0.5
Phosphorous (mg)	28- 52	17	17
Calcium (mg)	28 -38	36	36
Vitamin C (mg/100g)	2.0-8.2	6.0-12	0
Iron (mg)	C.L.A. Asadu, 5.5-11.6	D.O. Onagwu, 5.2	S. Hauser and C.C. Asadu 5.2

D. dumentorum, dihydrodioscorine, an extremely poisonous substance which causes general paralysis of the central nervous system has been isolated.

The substances responsible for yam pigment and flavor have also been isolated. Martin and Ruberte (1975) showed that the yellow flesh of *D. cayenensis* contains xanthophyll esters as the principal pigments which include neoxanthin, violaxanthin and auroxanthin. The anthocyanin pigments responsible for violet colour of *D. trifida* were identified as peonidin 3, 5-diglucoside, and malicidin 3, 5-diglucoside-ferulic acid (Carrino-Diaz and Grau, 1977).

12.Storage Issues

Due to the seasonality of yam production, the storage of the tubers for use during off-season time has attracted many research interests especially in relation to dormancy manipulation, control of storage pests and diseases. Dormancy was found to be a major important factor in yam storage because it determined the length of storage and related to the endogenous metabolic activity which in turn regulated carbohydrate breakdown (Passam, 1982). Passam also observed that the unsuccessful attempts to prolong dormancy by the application of sprout-suppressant chemicals were likely due to that sprouts were not formed until at late stage of dormancy and sprouts originated from beneath the peridorm. It was thus suggested that a more promising approach to prolonging dormancy and hence increasing the storage life of tubers is the application of

growth regulating hormones, in particular gibberellic acid. Kaku et al., (1984) outlined a technique based on transversal relaxation time of protons representing water molecules in a weak magnetic field for investigation of water content and the concentration and degree of polymerization of dissolved substances in tubers as a means of studying the phenomenon of dormancy.

Storing tubers at 150 °C and the use of gamma-radiation at doses between 7.5 and 15.0 krad inhibited sprouting of yams for six months (Adesuyi, 1977) after observing that chemical inhibitors were found ineffective. Martin (1977) also found that removing the growing shoots weekly increased the storage life of lesion free tubers up to 8 months. Martin further reported that wax and gibberellic acid treatment reduced weight loss and rate of sprouting. Adesuyi (1978) assessed the effect of cool storage and found that there was sprout suppression and great reduction in weight loss, and concluded that in terms of practicability in developing countries cool storage was more advantageous than ionizing radiation.

Ramamujam and Nair (1982) also observed that control of sprouting was a major constraint on storage of edible yams in India. Their study showed that soaking the tubers of *D. esculenta* and *D. rotundata* in 1000 ppm maleic hydrazide solution for 10 hours was found effective in controlling sprouting in stored yams. Further studies revealed that maleic hydrazide

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treatment did not affect seedling establishment, tuberization and tuber yield.

Igwilo et al. (1987) found that giberellic acid (GA₃) treatment delayed the sprouting of yam tubers by an average of 56 days in *D. rotundata* cv Nwokpo and 75 days in *D. alata* cv Um680 compared with untreated tubers. In some tubers of Um680, sprouting was suppressed for more than nine months after harvest (MAH). The study also showed that duration of inhibition varied with GA₃ concentration, tuber size, and ambient temperature, when the tubers were planted out as whole tubers, seed setts or minisetts under irrigation at 12 MAH they showed normal sprouting and development.

The incidence of rot in stored yams has been controlled with fungicides such as thiabendazole, benlate and captan while curing technique at temperature of 25 °C or 30 °C and low humidity between 55% and 62% for five days before storage was found to be effective in controlling rot in stored yam tubers (Adesuyi, 1973). The physiological process involved in wound repair during curing has been found to involve immediate migration of starch to the cut surface within 5 to 10 hrs of injury, formation of a suberized layer beneath the cut surface after 2-3 days and the production of periderm after about 5 days (Passam et al., 1976). Burying bruised yam tubers for 15 days before storage in the yam barn was found to result to reductions in weight loss (38%) and rotting (54%) after 4 months of storage compared with uncured tubers (Nnodu, 1987). The same study also

showed that the incidence of sprouting of cured tubers during storage increased as the curing duration increased. Hence it was concluded that burying bruised tubers in soil pits for 11-15 days was an effective curing technique for prolonging the shelf life of yam tubers.

Mignucci et al. (1984) indentified the major organisms associated with tuber decay in Puerto Rico to include fungi, nematode, soft rot, bacteria and white grubs. Their study showed that storing yams on raised slanting beds of bamboo reduced storage decay compared to commonly used soil surface storage. It was also shown that treatment with captan alone or with captan plus benomyl or plus thiabendazole resulted in more than 90% emergence compared to 52% for untreated pieces. Mantel and Haque (1978) found that the incidence of internal brown spot of *D. alata* was reduced by storing under high relative humidity (95±2%) but the tubers showed increased lesion size which impaired the quality of the tubers, thus this technique has a handicap.

Yams (*Dioscorea* spp.) are extremely important to food security because of their excellent storage properties; they can be stored for four to six months without refrigeration and provides an important food safety net between growing seasons (Aka et al., 2024).

13.Yam Improvement

Yam improvement especially breeding is a research area that has attracted the interest of many plant breeders but not much breakthrough had been recorded. Okoli (1981) found

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that white yam (*D. rotundata*) produced viable seeds implying that yam improvement by hybridization was possible but efforts to grow yams from seeds or vine cuttings had not so far resulted to practical replacement of the tubers as planting material (Oyolu, 1982). The results of breeding trials indicated that most of the clones of white yam *D. rotundata* did not yield as high as the local checks and most of the hybrid clones were deficient in at least one important characteristic such as vine vigour, vines and leaf spot resistance, tuber size, shape and nematode resistance (IITA, 1979).

Several factors have been identified as militating against genetic improvement in yams. According to Chinwuba (1971) the results from attempts to produce hybrid yam were not successful because yams seldom flower, and when they do, the flowers are too scanty, irregular and transient. Low percentage of fruit set, high frequency of aborted seeds and high degree of sterility had been identified as the major constraints on yam hybridization (IITA, 1979; Ene and Okoli, 1985). Again clonal multiplication of a sexual population of *D. rotundata*, all monoecious plants produced certain proportion of abnormal flowers which represented various transitional stages between the male and herm-phrodite flowers (Abraham and Nair, 1979). Earlier, Sadik and Okereke (1975) indicated that lack of success in hybridization efforts on yams were associated with those of flowering: a high male: female plant ratio, insect pollination and poor seed

germination through lack of an embryo or dormancy. Flowering between different clones of *D. alata* was synchronized through staggering of planting and intervarietal hybridization leading to some crosses resulting to some seed set under pollinated conditions but the absence of natural pollination constituted a major hindering factor (Bai and Jos 1986).

The yam meristem culture (Ng and Hahn, 1985) developed at IITA showed that the requirements for *D. rotundata* and *D. alata* were different, the tissue of the former developed in the plantlets while that of the latter did better with high concentration of gibberellic acid. The small size of the meristem and the blackening of the explants and the culture media were thought to have led to the poor development of the plantlet.

Breeding efforts especially at IITA were generally more successful with *D. alata* than with any other variety though large numbers of biotypes of *D. rotundata* had been obtained at IITA through sexual propagation (López-Montes et al., 2021). This was said to provide an opportunity for investigating the possibility of identifying high-protein yams among large number of segregate. Improved families and lines of *D. rotundata* had also been reported at IITA (Asfaw et al., 2024), hence work on breeding for various qualities such as virus and nematode resistance, high yield and good quality tubers is still being tried.

Wilson (1982) reviewed the various techniques in yam improvement and noted that for

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genetically variable population, breeding can only be attained through sexual propagation. For clonal propagation, rooted cuttings require high humidity facilities and certain degree of skill and close attention to detail and was, therefore most appropriate for research purposes. For all root crops, Jackson (1984) pointed out that the indirect importation of germplasm as a vegetative planting material should be considered a high risk and that there should be intermediate quarantine of the materials. Chinwuba (1971) had earlier opined that in view of these problems associated with yam breeding increase in yam yields may better be achieved by concentrating researches on agronomic aspects rather than breeding. However, Onwueme (1982) proposed a package for the ideal yam culture of the future as follows- the yams are to be grown on ridges from small setts planted at close spacing, pre-emergence herbicide to be used to control early weed, stakes will not be used and harvesting will be done mechanically and only at the end of the season. This package would drastically reduce the high labour requirements in mounding, staking and hand harvesting though large ware yams may not be envisaged, a situation that some present yam farmers may not compromise.

Mulching plays a pivotal role in modern sustainable agriculture, offering a versatile solution to enhance soil quality, improve soil health, conserve resources, and optimize crop performance (Kumar et al., 2024). From the

study organic compost mulch significantly increased soil pH and soil electrical conductivity (EC). The control treatment resulted in the highest soil moisture content, while the highest soil temperatures were recorded for the black polythene and organic compost mulch treatments. The organic compost mulch enhanced the soil organic carbon (SOC) content, soil available phosphorus (SAP) content, and soil exchangeable calcium (SECa) content. The weedmat mulch showed the highest soil exchangeable potassium (SEK) content, and the control treatment exhibited the highest soil exchangeable magnesium (SEMg) and sodium (SENa) content. In terms of micronutrients, the sawdust mulch and black polythene mulch significantly increased soil exchangeable iron (SEFe) and copper (SECu) levels, respectively. Notable seasonal variations in soil pH, temperature, and environmental humidity were observed during the crop period. The soil pH fluctuated from slightly acidic levels in August 2023 to neutral levels in October, and then decreased to slightly acidic levels in early 2024 before stabilizing by March 2024. The soil temperature peaked in November and dropped in January, while the environmental humidity ranged from 48.25% in December to 76.33% in February. The study demonstrated that the organic compost mulch stood out as an advantageous choice because of its capacity to enhance the soil's properties and offer a balanced nutrient mix, making it particularly beneficial for yam cultivation. It also proved to

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be a reliable and balanced option to enhance soil quality with stable soil quality indices (SQIs). The weedmat mulch proved to be highly effective in enhancing yam growth and productivity. The weedmat mulch is the most profitable and cost-effective option for yam cultivation, providing the highest net returns and strong financial viability. This study emphasizes the value of choosing the right mulching materials to support soil quality, crop productivity, and economic returns in tropical settings, making strides toward more sustainable farming practices (Kumar et al., 2024).

Cover crops and crop rotations play a vital role in maintaining and enhancing soil health in yam farming systems. Cover crops, such as legumes, can fix atmospheric nitrogen, improve soil structure, and increase organic matter content, which are beneficial for subsequent yam crops. Crop rotations, particularly those involving legumes or cereals, can break pest and disease cycles, reduce soil erosion, and improve nutrient cycling (Pouya et al., 2022). For instance, rotating yams with cereals or legumes has been shown to stabilize yields and improve

soil carbon stocks, which are critical for long-term soil fertility. Additionally, incorporating cover crops and crop residues into the soil can enhance microbial activity and nutrient availability, further supporting sustainable yam production (Agegnehu and Amede, 2017).

Precision agriculture (PA) has emerged as a transformative approach in yam production, leveraging advanced technologies to optimize resource use and enhance crop yields. PA utilizes sensors, IoT, and machine learning to monitor soil conditions, crop health, and environmental factors, enabling precise interventions that improve productivity and sustainability (Cisternas et al., 2020; Sharma et al., 1989). Remote sensors and wireless sensor networks (WSN) are particularly effective in gathering real-time data on soil moisture, organic carbon, and crop health, which can be used to make informed decisions about irrigation, fertilization, and pest control. The integration of high-resolution imagery from satellites or drones further aids in monitoring crop conditions and predicting yields, thus reducing human labor and increasing efficiency (Shafi et al., (2019) , Figure 3).

Figure 3: The application of precision agriculture in Chinese yam production (Adopted from Sharma et al., 1989)

14. Comparative Economic Analysis

Asumugha et al. (2007) carried out a study on the comparative economic analysis of seed yam production techniques in Nigeria. This study aimed at assessing the economics of three seed yam production techniques (milking, minisett and minituber) to the farmer. Results showed that the three techniques will return more than 100% (Nigerian Currency invested). Going by the return per naira generated, milking technique appeared most profitable followed by minisett. Again on seed yam supply in Nigeria (Asumugha et al., 2009) reported that there were no commercial structures for supply of seed yam in Nigeria. The rural assemblers and wholesalers limit purchases and supplies to accessible rural markets and farmers only sell seed yams after satisfying own requirements.

An experiment was conducted at Umudike, Nigeria by Ogbonna et al. (2011) to evaluate the profitability of minituber production technique

using selected improved white yam varieties developed in 2003 as a back up to the minisett technique. The three white yam varieties selected were TDr89/02677, TDr89/02665 and TDr89/02565 known for their high potential yield. Setts of 8-10 grams were planted directly in the field for two years with spacing of 10cm x 100cm between ridges 10cm x 20cm between rows on a ridge (double row) and 10cm x 10cm intra row. The data were collected using cost route approach and were analysed using descriptive statistical and Net return analysis. The result on establishment count on average of 4 weeks after planting (WAP) + 8 weeks after planting (WAP) showed that TDr89/02677, TDr89/02665 and TDr89/02565) gave 52.2, 46.1 and 43.5% sprout count while percentage stand count were 63.0, 53.9 and 52.2% respectively. The result of the profitability of the study showed that the three improved yam varieties (TDr89/02677, TDr89/02665 and TDr89/02565) were profitable as incomes generated were N141, 100.00, N49, 900.00 and N46, 300.00 respectively and on average gave an income of N79, 100.00.

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Socio-economic studies on yam production conducted in Nigeria assumed different dimensions including Lageman (1977), Bachman (1981), Eluagu and Chinaka (1985), Dorosh (1988), Ezeh et al., (1992) and Ezeh (1994, 1998). Lageman (1977) compared the contribution of yam among other crops to framers' income and found that yams constituted an average of 32% of farmers' gross income. Bachman (1981) was interested in investigating the problems and trends of yam holdings, while Eluagu and Chinaka (1985) were more concerned with the economics of different staking methods. Details Edwards and Cropper (1987) in the West Indies and Lyonga (1981) in Cameroon have shown that despite the high production costs, yam production is profitable.

Results of a two-year (2008 and 2009) study at the University of Uyo Teaching and Research Farm, Nigeria, (Ikeh et al., 2012) indicated significant differences in all the yield and yield components of the different eight yam genotypes considered in both years. The cost of production in 2009 was 2% above the cost of production in 2008 due to increase in cost of land preparation. The cost-benefit ratio of all the genotypes were above 10.00 except in local variety, Eteme with values of 4.9 and 6.3 in 2008 and 2009, respectively. The average cost-benefit ratio of 14.25 recorded by the genotype TDr 95/18894 suggested strongly that the genotype was more adaptable to Uyo agro-ecology than others.

Eyitayo et al (2010) conducted a study in Oyo State, Nigeria on the economics of seed yam production using the minisett technique and found that the total cost of production was N150, 500 per hectare while the cost per seed yam was N16.72. The total revenue per hectare of seed yam production was N337, 500, thus, for every naira invested farmers were expected to have N1.24 net returns. This shows that seed yam production using the minisett technique was a profitable venture in the study area. The study also revealed that labour alone accounted for 78.1% of the production cost. Hence appropriate technologies to reduce labour cost would increase the profitability of seed yams production using the minisett technique.

An earlier similar study (Ezeh, 1994) conducted at Umudike in Southeastern Nigeria showed seed yam production required labour inputs of about 218 man A days/ha or 86.3 man-days plus 9.4 tractor hours/t of seed. From the study, the estimated gross margin per hectare and net income per ha were - 4 472.16 Naira and - 5 120.16 Naira, respectively, suggesting that the production was unprofitable. These findings have implications for the management of a commercial seed yam production venture, thus for profitable production, the entrepreneur should minimize the use of resource inputs and, thus lower production costs, and/or maximize yields, thereby, increasing revenue.

On the adoption of yam minisett technology in the middle belt region of Nigeria; Ayoola (2012) showed that 98.33 percent of farmers were

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aware of the technology while only 9.32 percent adopted the technology. The probit analysis indicated that age of the farmers, farm size, and years of farming experience, amount of credit available and frequency of extension contacts were positively related to adoption and would probably increase the adoption of the improved yam minisett technology. A study on the effect of improved yam variety on the productivity and farm income of farming households in Guinea savanna, Nigeria (Awoniyi and Awoyinka, 2007) showed that improved yam variety led to the increases in productivity of yam enterprise among farming households and income received from the output from the improved variety, as well as the welfare of the yam farmers in terms of purchasing power through enhanced income.

Akinola and Owombo (2011) conducted a study on the economics of adoption of mulching technology in yam production in Osun State, Nigeria. This study used a multi-stage sampling technique to select 105 farmers involving adopters and non-adopters of mulching technology. Data were analyzed with the aid of descriptive statistics, budgetary techniques and probit model. The results of budgetary analysis showed that seed yam and labour costs constituted significant parts of the variable costs. The average revenue per hectare for adopters was N412, 971.69 while that of non-adopters was N346, 456.75. However, the average net incomes were N326, 865.02 and N236, 087.40 for the adopters and non-

adopters, respectively. The benefit-cost ratios were 4.79 and 3.13 for adopters and non-adopters, respectively. The probit model revealed that household size and hired labour were significant factors determining the farmers' adoption decisions. There was therefore the need to encourage farmers to adopt the land protecting technology and recommended that a policy thrust that would make seed yam available and affordable and reduce the costs incurred on labour would be in the right direction.

Ike and Inoni (2006) conducted a study in to investigate the determinants of yam production in Southeastern Nigeria using a stochastic frontier production function, which incorporated a model of inefficiency effects. Farm-level data were collected from a sample of 120 yam farmers in Enugu State and used for the analysis. The results indicated that labour and material inputs were the major factors that influenced changes in yam output. The effects of selected farmer-specific socio-economic characteristics on observed inefficiencies among the farmers were also examined. Farmer-specific variables, such as education, farming experience and access to credit, were the significant factors implicated for the observed variation inefficiency among yam producers.

Shehu et al., (2010) conducted a similar study in Benue State, Nigeria to investigate the determinants of yam production and technical efficiency of yam farmers using the same methodology. The empirical results indicated

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that land, seed yam, family labour and fertilizer were the major factors that influenced changes in yam output. Farmer-specific variables such as education, membership of association and household size were found to have significant effects on the observed variation in technical efficiency among the yam producers. The technical efficiency of farmers varied from 0.67 to 0.99 with a mean of 0.95. The implication of the study was that efficiency in yam production among the farmers could be increased by 5% through better use of land, seed yam, family labour and fertilizer in the short term given the prevailing state of technology.

Izekor and Olumese (2010) conducted a study to examine the determinants of yam production and profitability in Edo State, Nigeria. Data used for the study were obtained using structured questionnaire administered to 120 randomly selected yam farmers from Ovia South West and Ovia North East Local Government Area of the state. Descriptive statistics, Gross Margin analysis and Production function analysis using the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) criterion was used to estimate the parameters of the production function. The result of the budgetary analysis revealed that yam production was profitable in the study area with an average gross margin of N58, 400. Farm size, staking, yam setts and the operating cost were found to be positively related to output, with labour as the major determinant. The result further showed a return to scale of 4.582 indicating an increasing return to scale, implying inefficiency

in the use of resources in the enterprise as production was in the irrational stage (stage 1) of production.

Kalu and Erhabor (1992) conducted a study in a tropical guinea savanna location, Nigeria to assess the production and economic attributes of a local variety of white Guinea yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir.) minisetts under two production systems - planting on ridges and on beds at the same plant population density of 40,000 stands/ha during the 1987 to 1989 production seasons. The bed system improved emergence percentage (E %) by eleven (11), stand establishment by 18 % and gave 28 % increase in total tuber production over the ridge system. An average of 67% of total harvested tubers was classified as ware yams (401 - 3,000 g under the bed system and 77 % as seed yams (less than 400 g) under the ridge system. Based on gross margin analysis, the economic returns from the bed system was 275 % more than returns from the ridge system, due in part to the high proportion of the more valuable ware yams realized from the bed system. On both technical and economic grounds, the bed system was superior to the ridge system.

Emokaro and Law-Ogbomo (2008) conducted a study in Edo State, Nigeria to compared the influence of different minisetts sizes (ranging from 25g to 50g) on the profit realizable from yam production in the Forest and Forest-Savanna transition zones of Edo State, with the main objective of determining the optimum level of returns with respect to the minisetts

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sizes. The randomized complete block design involving six miniset sizes (25, 30, 35, 40, 45 and 50g) in four replicates was employed in examining the output from the two zones covered in this study. The result of the analysis indicated that the total production cost per hectare increased with increasing sett size, ranging from \$1822.43 for the 25g sett to \$2942.43.00 for the 50g sett respectively for the two zones. The economic returns also increased with increasing miniset size for the two zones, with the highest gross margin and net returns of \$12909.57 and \$12622.78 respectively from the 50g sett size recorded in the Forest-Savanna zone. In the Forest zone, a gross margin of \$12648.70 and net returns of \$12361.91 were obtained from the 50g sett size. Optimum returns from the different miniset sizes however, differed in both zones, based on the viability indices of returns per dollar invested which amounted to \$4.75 under the miniset size of 40g and \$5.43 under miniset size of 30g at the Forest and Forest-Savanna transition zones, respectively.

Law-Ogbomo and Emokaro (2009) conducted another study to investigate the effect of different rates of NPK 15:15:15 fertilizer application on the yield of yam in three different ecological zones of Edo State with the aim of determining the optimal fertilizer application rate and the most profitable ecological zone for yam production in Edo State. The study involved the use of *Dioscorea rotundata* Poir, fertilized with NPK (15:15:15) at

rates of 0, 100, 200,300 and 400 kg/ha using a randomized complete block design with three replicates. The crop was planted early (April) 2004 and 2005 in each of the ecological zones (Derived Savanna (Ubiaja), Forest-Savanna transition (Sabongidda-Ora) and Forest (Evboneka)). Based on the objective function of profit maximization, the optimum returns were recorded at a fertilizer application rate of 300 kg/ha in the Derived Savanna zone with a gross margin of \$18,577.38, net returns of \$18,225.21 and a benefit-cost ratio of 5.10. In the Forest-Savanna transition zone, optimum rate of fertilizer application was also at 300 kg/ha with a gross margin of \$13,794.78 and benefit cost ratio of 3.76. Optimum rate of fertilizer application, however, dropped to 200 kg/ha in the Forest zone with a gross margin of \$13457.39, net returns of \$13110.61 and benefit-cost ratio of 3.73. This showed that the farmers in the Derived Savanna and Forest-Savanna transition zones were in a better position to make more profit from yam production through the application of higher rates of fertilizer than farmers in the forest zone. However, soils in the forest zones were naturally fertile and as such required lower fertilizer application rates than in the other zones.

15. Major Constraints on Yam Production

Agbaje and Aluko (2009) did a research work on analyses of hybrid yam (*Dioscorea rotundata* Poir) on-farm trials in southwestern Nigeria and reported that hybrid yam without staking had significantly higher yield compared to local

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variety. Staking is one of the major cultural practices used in yam production that has attracted the interest of researchers. Doku (1967) observed that the effect of staking differed according to cultivar and location but reported that higher yields were often obtained from staked than unstaked plots. Okigbo (1973) found that staking increased tuber size and yield because it improved the exposure of the leaves to sunlight. According to Nwankiti (1982) staking keeps vines and leaves away from the soil and protects the plant from anthracnose-causing organisms which have been found to survive in the soil from one season to another. Similarly Loyonga (1985) reported that staking led to longer leaf duration in water logged areas and hence better yields. Gollifer (1973) also attributed the higher yields obtained from staked than unstaked yams to longer leaf area duration and more efficient foliage display. To help reduce cost of staking a new minimum staking method where the yam vines were trained on a nylon netting about 50cm above ground had been suggested (IITA, 1982).

Nweke (1981) states categorically that relative to other crops, yam production is labour as well as capital intensive. As earlier reported the major constraints on the supply of yam were high cost planting material and excessive labour requirement for staking, weeding and harvesting (Veter and Bečvářová, 2015; Coursey and Booth, 1977). Staking which is done to save yam tendrils and leaves from the heat of the soil and extend leaf duration is laborious because,

according to Nweke, (1981), it involves not only cutting suitable stakes from the bush before actually staking but trailing the yam tendrils on the stakes.

Certain factors have been identified through research as militating against increased yam production. Yams are costly to produce because of the large quantity of seed material required for planting, the large number of stakes required for the support of the vines and the high number of man drays required for their cultivation (Enyi, 1970). Other factors that were specific to Africa according to Enyi were time of planting, size and spacing of planting materials, improper staking and decline in the use of organic manures and low use of artificial fertilizers to improve soil fertility coupled with intercropping which was the usual cropping pattern. The major determinants of yam production in Southeastern Nigeria were labour and material inputs (Ike and Inoni, 2006). Gebremeskel and Ngambuki (n, d) observed that one of the major problems in the development of root and tuber crops was the poor allocation of funds by government compared to other crops. In the Upper Volta, Dumont (1977) identified two factors that had negative effects in tuber crop production as the non-existent outlets due to lack of market organizations and the preference shown by the Voltans for cereals as well as the underdevelopment of the entire agricultural system.

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Yam is an important staple food crop of high socio-cultural and ritual significance in the yam belts (rainforest and derived savannah zone) of the country, particularly in the lowland belt of the River Niger. According to FAO report 1997, lack of reliable supply of good quality seed yams and other enabling factors have led to a considerable decline in productivity since 1971 and consequently a progressive decrease in the area under cultivation. The scarcity and high cost of planting materials for yam (seed yams) constitute major constraints in yam production. Attempt made by Nwoke and Okonkwo (1978) to find a solution to the problem of planting material through the use of mother tubers removed (milked) from the yam stands could not function. This was because the cumulative yields obtained from the original plant plus the one from the replanted tuber was either similar or even less than the yield from un milked plants. The minisett technique (Otoo et al., 2019) appeared to be the only viable economic option for seed yam production at present.

Inadequate supply of yams to consumers is due to constraints arising from production and storage. Verter and Bečvářová (2015) stated that though yam is a prestigious item of food meant for the affluent, it is not extensively cultivated like cassava particularly because of high cost of production due to high cost of seed yams and intensive labour involved. Oyolu (1984) noted that the cost of propagule accounts for more than 50% of total cost of ware yam production but indicated that the reproductive coefficient

$[100 \times (\text{gross yield-seed rate})/\text{seed rate}]$ was usually less than 300. Diehl (1982) observed that the availability of yam setts was not only limited by the low rate of reproduction but also by the households' subsistence demands.

Attempts so far made on the mechanization of yam production were not yet perfected. The basic requirements for mechanization were compact, medium sized and regularly shaped tubers (Anonymous, 1972). These conditions were yet far from being reached. Jeffers (1977) reported an attempt made in Barbados to construct a local planter for yam planting which was not very successful. Even the locally constructed aid and imported digger-elevator used for harvesting only worked for sweet potatoes but not for yams unless modified. However, Ferguson (1970) earlier reported that a mechanical side-lifter which exposed the tubers had been developed by the University of West Indies and has been used successfully in harvesting *D. alata* cv white lisbon yam and *D. esculenta* (Chinese yam).

Genomics and biotechnology have significantly advanced yam breeding and cultivation practices. Predictive breeding techniques had been employed to develop yam varieties with improved traits such as disease resistance, drought tolerance, and higher nutritional value (Wu, 2024). These techniques involved profiling parent traits, smart crossing, and selecting individuals with superior attributes, which were then tested in target environments for commercial deployment (Asfaw et al., 2019).

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Additionally, the development of nematode-resistant cultivars and varieties adapted to low soil fertility were key innovations that addressed some of the major constraints in yam production. These biotechnological advancements not only enhanced yam productivity but also contributed to food security and poverty reduction in yam-growing regions (Mignouna et al., 2020).

The use of smart machinery and automation in yam production could revolutionize traditional farming practices. Farm machinery and intelligent irrigation systems could reduce the need for manual labor and increase operational efficiency. Automated systems for planting, harvesting, and post-harvest processing being developed by Kiba et al., (2020) might help streamline yam production processes. The intelligent harvesting techniques and drip irrigation systems could ensure optimal water use and reduce wastage; thereby enhancing overall productivity and these innovations are particularly beneficial in regions with labor shortages and challenging climatic conditions, as they help maintain consistent and high-quality yields (Kiba et al., 2020).

Other factors constraining yam production such as cost of planting material, planting of low yielding varieties/species, poor soil fertility, pests and diseases in field and storage have been implicated as responsible for the decline in yam production in many regions. Kenyon (2006) reported that the cause of this decline is often cited as being the declining soil fertility

due to shorter fallow periods and use of more marginal land for yam production because of the increasing demand on agriculture to feed the increasing human population. Besides, yam was also the most expensive root crop to produce because of high cost of labour demand for land preparation, planting, staking, weeding harvesting and transport to market (Kenyon, 2006). Earlier Degras, (1993) had stated that yam production was adversely affected by many factors among which are: limited availability and cost of planting material, high cost of labour for operations like land preparation, staking, weeding, harvesting, storage, pest and diseases. The most important climatic elements for crop growth and yield including yams which are not easily controlled include radiant energy, or solar radiation, temperature and water or rainfall (Ekaputa, 2004). Solar radiation in turn determines the thermal characteristics of the environment, namely net radiation, day-length or photoperiod and the air and soil temperatures (Danjuma, 2004). All crops have minimum, optimum and maximum climatic limits in their developmental stages. Soil and air temperatures affect the developmental stages more than any other factor (Ayoade, 2002).

Constraints due to rainfall, moisture and temperature had also been highlighted. Crop production in the tropics as in other parts of the world is sensitive to environmental factors (Ohiri, 1995). The major climatic parameters involved in yam production are rainfall, temperature, light, and photoperiod (Degras,

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1993). Moisture and temperature remains the most critical agro-meteorological factor for crop production in the tropics. Olasantan (1999) reported that mulching was very important in yam cultivation for soil temperature regulation. Soil temperature between 25 to 30 °C was found suitable for yam growth (Ohiri, 1995). Yam tuber yield and growth were found to reduce with increase in soil bulk density above 1.1g/cm³ (Ferguson and Gumbs, 1976) and increased soil density has been found to reduce uptake of N, P, K, Ca and Mg by yam (Agbede and Ojeniyi, 2003).

Diby et al. (2009) reported that rainfall amount and distribution affected yam productivity. The fresh tuber yield and the area under the curve (AUC) of tuber dry matter in both yam species (*D. rotundata* and *D. alata*) studied were highest in the most humid growing season 2001. However, limited rainfall experienced during the growth phases II and III in 2002 probably explained the lower fresh tuber yield and shoot and tuber dry matter AUC in that growing season. According to them water limitation was more marked in *D. rotundata* compared to *D. alata*. Craufurd et al. (2001) also reported that growth phases of yams were highly sensitive to water stress in their study.

Constraints due to tillage systems used in yam production had also attracted the attention of yam researcher. Many researches had been conducted in Nigeria on response of yam to tillage techniques but many of them produced inconclusive and controversial results. For

instance Onwueme (1978) found no significant difference in yam tuber yield between planting on mounds and ridges while Agbede and Ojeniyi (2003) reported that mounding produced higher tuber weight and tuber length compared with ridging. Odjugo (2007) did a research on the effect of tillage systems and mulching on soil microclimate, growth and yield of white yam (*Dioscorea rotundata*) in Midwestern Nigeria and observed that mulched treatment had significantly higher soil moisture than unmulched and soil temperature at 0-10 cm in mound was significantly higher than in ridge and hole tillage. However, the study showed that yam tuber yield was significantly higher in mound tillage (16.1 t ha⁻¹) followed by ridge (14.2 t ha⁻¹) and hole tillage (9.0 t ha⁻¹). Odjugo concluded that partially mulched treatment (15.4 t ha⁻¹) significantly produced more tubers than the unmulched (12.9 t ha⁻¹) and mulched treatment (11.4 t ha⁻¹).

Odjugo (2008) repeated a similar research but on yellow yam (*Dioscorea cayenensis*) and reported that soil moisture at 0-15 cm depth was significantly higher in zero tillage (40 g/g), followed by ridge (30 g/g) and mound (24 g/g) but the reverse was the case with soil temperature where mound tillage (34.2°C) had the highest temperature followed by ridge (31.4°C) and zero (29.5°C). The study also showed that mulching significantly influenced the soil microclimatic condition enhancing yam emergence while soil temperatures favoured the growth, leaf area accumulation and yield.

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From Odjugo (2008) mound tillage significantly gave the highest yam tuber yield (12.0 t/ha-1), followed by ridge (8.8 t/ha-1) and zero (5.0 t/ha-1); while partially mulched treatment significantly produced the highest yam tubers (10.3 t/ha-1), followed by the unmulched (8.1 t/ha-1) and mulched (7.4 t/ha-1) treatments. Mound tillage that is partially mulched is recommended for the production of ware yams.

Also a research on the effects of seedbed types on yam-minisettis yield in Ushongo local government area of Benue state of Nigeria showed that the raised, flattened top beds improved yield of minisettis by 21% over the ridge system (Ijoyah et. al., 2006). The findings were attributed to that the nutrients applied were secured in place on raised flat beds and did not experience any soil wash or leaching so that the roots appropriately absorbed the nutrients thereby enhancing the weight of tubers. The results also showed that the bed system improved total tuber number by 24% compared to ridges this was attributed to the seedbed structure and its ability to retain moisture and nutrient concluding that the raised flattened top beds not only provided simple depth of loose, fertile soil for tuber and root penetration, but were less readily washed away by rain during the course of the season compared to ridges.

According to Adeleye et al., (2011) yam tuber yield parameters were significantly influenced ($p < 0.05$) by soil tillage techniques (ploughing

(P), ploughing plus harrowing (PH), manual ridging (MR), manual heaping (MH) and zero-tillage (ZT). Yam tuber yield parameters were better enhanced in manually ridged and heaped plots than other tillage techniques in the study. The tuber yield obtained was in the order of $MH > MR > P > PH > ZT$. Tuber yield from manually ridged plots was not significantly different from the yield obtained from manually heaped plots. According to them higher yields obtained from manually heaped and ridged plots might be due to the fact that manually tilled plots had lower bulk density and higher total porosity which might have improved root penetration and tuber induction in the soil.

Constraints associated with mulching practices in yam production have also been reported. Mulching is a long old traditional practice in yam cultivation aimed at controlling soil temperature and heat scorching in addition maintaining good soil physical conditions by conserving soil moisture and enhancing water infiltration and stabilizing soil structure. Mulching improves biotic activity and adds nutrients to soil thereby improving soil fertility (Awodun and Ojeniyi, 1999; Ojeniyi and Adetoro (1993). Mulching was also found to increase yield of crops such as yam and cocoyam (Hulugalle et al, 1985; Igwilllo, 2001). A research on the effect of mulching on soil temperature and moisture regime on emergence, growth and yield of white yam in a tropical wet-and-dry climate showed that mulching significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased

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emergence rate of yam by 46% and tuber yield by about 6-8 tonnes ha⁻¹ than the unmulched plots (Eruola et al., 2012). Detailed study on the effects of mulching on soil temperature, moisture and physico-chemical properties and the yield of root crops carried out in different areas in Nigeria (Halugalle et al., 1985; Halugalle et al., 1990; Okoh, 2004) reported significant positive effects.

Adeniyani et al., (2008) conducted a research on the relative effect of weed mulch types on soil properties and yield of yam in southwest Nigeria and observed that mulching materials significantly reduced soil temperature. The study showed that mulch materials from Mexican sunflower and Siam weed significantly increased the soil moisture content and were more effective in improving moisture content, reducing temperature and soil bulk density than materials from guinea grass and elephant grass. Though all the mulches increased tuber weight and length significantly, the Mexican sunflower and Siam weed mulches gave higher performance of yam. At 10t/ha, Mexican sunflower and Siam weed mulches increased tuber weight by 57%, while guinea grass and elephant grass mulches increased it by 29%. The positive effects of the mulch materials were attributed to improved availability of K in the soil, reduced soil temperature, reduced soil bulk density and enhanced soil moisture content (Adeniyani et al., 2008).

Acheampong et al., (2020) identified constraints on the supply of seed yams for

intensive yam production as diseases and pest infestations as well as the unavailability of quality planting material and recommended a combination of tissue culture and aeroponics system as the way towards clean and adequate supply of seed yam for enhanced yam production. However, the system was also considered as expensive for any individual to implement from the economic analysis they performed using data from established tissue culture and aeroponics system in Ghana. They recommended that for food security and creation of workplaces, government could partner with the private sector in the establishment of aeroponics systems to increase yam production and export. Balogun et al., (2021) documented a comprehensive method towards resolving the problem of seed yam scarcity by the use of Drip System Hydroponics (DSH) and stated that all classes of seed yam can be produced using the system depending on what was initially planted ranging from Breeder to Foundation to Certified seed.

The emerging technology on use of sacks for yam production is attracting research attention to help resolve some constraints on yam production. Veggiegrow (2025) defined yam sack farming is the growing of yam in sacks in backyards, gardens, rooftops and enables people to practice urban farming without buying a farmland or renting a farmland to grow yams. Yam sack farming is a vertical farming concept that can produce more yam tubers per square metre as compared to

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growing yams on farms. It can provide employment opportunities for the people improve the level of yam production and enhance urban farming and healthy living. Noah (2014) found that to get good tuber size of yam, its planting materials must be planted on a fertile medium composed of topsoil, dried grasses and organic manure. The technique saves the time and energy involved in land clearance and construction of ridges and heaps for yam planting in addition to energy and time spent on weeding all resulting in ease of effective management and space conservation.

Labor optimization and mechanization are critical for enhancing yam productivity. The study conducted in Ebonyi State, Nigeria, reported that hired labor significantly impacts multi-factor productivity, reducing it by 1.05% (Chukwuemeka et al., 2019) suggesting that optimizing labor use and integrating mechanization could alleviate labor constraints and improve productivity. Additionally, the introduction of mechanized farming practices could address issues such as inadequate land and high transportation costs, which were significant barriers to increased yam production (Chukwuemeka et al., 2019). Mechanization not only reduced the labor burden but also enhanced efficiency and productivity, making it a vital component of modern yam cultivation strategies.

Agricultural extension services and farmer skill development are pivotal in improving yam productivity. A research had indicated that

contact with extension agents was a significant determinant of technical efficiency in yam production (Ismail and Mahmud, 2023). Farmers with regular extension contact tended to adopt better farming practices, leading to higher productivity. In Rivers and Imo States, Nigeria, the study found that dedicated extension agents and accessible credit facilities were crucial for increasing yam productivity (Odinwa et al., 2019). The findings suggested that enhancing the frequency and quality of extension services could equip farmers with the necessary skills and knowledge to adopt improved yam cultivation techniques, thereby boosting productivity.

Market access and economic incentives play a crucial role in supporting yam productivity. The economic viability of yam investment in sub-Saharan Africa and beyond was found to be significant, with potential economic returns ranging between US\$584 and US\$1392 million (Mignouna et al., 2020). This underscored the importance of creating economic incentives for farmers to adopt new technologies and practices. Additionally, improving market access and optimizing the supply chain could address constraints such as high transportation costs and inadequate storage facilities, which hindered yam production (Kiba et al., 2020). By enhancing market access and providing economic incentives, farmers could achieve better profitability and sustainability in yam cultivation.

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In West Africa, various agronomic practices had been tested to enhance yam yield. For instance, a study conducted across different environmental gradients in Côte d'Ivoire and Burkina Faso found that fertilization regimes, particularly the combination of organic and mineral fertilization, positively impacted soil surface cover but had a weak impact on tuber yields. The study also highlighted the importance of rainfall and soil carbon stocks as key determinants of tuber yields (Pouya et al., 2022). In Ghana, the incorporation of pigeonpea residue into the soil significantly increased yam yields, with the highest yields obtained under this treatment compared to other management practices such as continuous unfertilized rainfed yam and yam with added fertilizer (Liu et al., 2021). In Nigeria, factorial trials revealed that increasing yam plant density consistently improved tuber yields, while intercropping with maize reduced yam yields significantly. Additionally, the use of improved seed tubers in Benin led to a yield increase of 22-27% and a gain in profitability of 30~40% for different yam species.

The analysis of various yield improvement strategies indicated that integrated nutrient management and proper agronomic practices were crucial for enhancing yam productivity. In Moluccas, intensive tillage combined with complete NPK fertilization resulted in the highest yield of local yam tubers, demonstrating the effectiveness of both soil preparation and balanced fertilization (Waas et al., 2020). In

West Africa, a transdisciplinary approach involving the development and testing of new soil and plant management technologies in collaboration with local stakeholders led to significant increases in yam productivity. This participatory research approach ensured that the technologies were well-adapted to the local biophysical and socio-economic contexts (Kiba et al., 2020). Furthermore, staking methods and appropriate nitrogen doses were found to be essential for maximizing yam yield and quality, with single staking and a nitrogen dose of 120.70 kg/ha being recommended for optimal productivity. Staking also reduced soil loss due to crop harvesting and associated carbon loss, thereby contributing to environmental sustainability.

Generally, the importance of site-specific management practices is evident, as factors such as rainfall, soil carbon stocks, and local agronomic conditions significantly influence yam yields. Integrated nutrient management, including the use of organic and mineral fertilizers, is essential for sustaining soil health and improving crop productivity. The adoption of improved seed tubers and appropriate planting techniques can lead to substantial yield and profitability gains, highlighting the need for investment in yam seed systems as reported by Cornet et al., (2023). Participatory and transdisciplinary research approaches that involve local stakeholders were also considered crucial for developing and promoting sustainable yam production practices (Gokul et

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al., 2023). These insights can be applied more broadly to enhance yam yields in other regions with similar agro-ecological conditions, thereby improving food security and livelihoods for smallholder farmers.

16. Conclusions

The one percent (six) of the 600 species of Dioscoreaceae reported to be economically important staple species is a serious challenge to agronomist and plant scientists in the world. Domestication of wild species is the key challenge as the forests where they are found are fast disappearing.

The popularity of yam as the most preferred starchy staple in the yam belt of West Africa is spreading to all parts of the world because there is hardly any part of the world one would not find people from the yam belt of West Africa. Increased yam production, processing and marketing are key challenges.

Yam production can be expanded beyond the countries of West Africa because many other tropical regions of the world have the biophysical environments required for the good

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performance of yam. Food culture and economics of production may constitute challenges on introducing yam production in those countries not currently known for yam production.

The numerous constraints facing yam production currently including labour, input materials, pests and diseases, market access and processing appear to overwhem the few yam researchers in the world. Encouraging young agriculturists to acquire higher degrees in yam research may help because the researches often take longer time to achieve results than most other staple crops due to the long gestation period of yam. Currently funds for yam research are hardly available. Establishment of more Yam Research Institutes should be encouraged.

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